

Título	Autor	Ano	Base	Status
Enhancing algorithmic assessment in education: Equi-fused-data-based SMOTE for balanced learning	Yasmine Chachoui and Nabiha Azizi and Richard Hotte and Tahar Bensebaa	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Gamified feedback in adaptive retrieval practice: Points and progress-bars enhance motivation but not learning	Gesa S. E. {van den Broek} and Stefanie Scholten and Bente {van Thuil} and Hedderik {van Rijn} and Tamara {van Gog} and Maarten {van der Velde}	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
A comparative analysis of programming games, looking through the lens of an instructional design model and a game attributes taxonomy	Lieve Laporte and Bieke Zaman	2018	Science@Direct	Accepted
Learning about serious game design and development at the K-12 level	Bill Kapralos	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Cultivating thinking skills and computational thinking in higher education: A case-based decision-support model from Taiwan	Shih-Jui Chang and Chin-Tsai Lin and Yung-Hui Chen	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Reasons to Engage in and Learning Experiences From Different Play Strategies in a Web-Based Serious Game on Delirium for Medical Students: Mixed Methods Design	Kiki R Buijs-Spanjers and Harianne HM Hegge and Fokie Cnossen and Debbie ADC Jaarsma and Sophia E {de Rooij}	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Evaluating and validating the Serious Slow Game Jam methodology as a mechanism for co-designing serious games to improve understanding of cybersecurity for different demographics	Shenando Stals and Lynne Baillie and Ryan Shah and Jamie Iona Ferguson and Manuel Maarek	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Artificial intelligence in computer programming education: A systematic literature review	Pisut Manorat and Suppawong Tuarob and Siripen Pongpaichet	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Incorporating customization and personalization into game-based learning: A cognitive style perspective	Oskar Ku and Chi-Chen Hou and Sherry Y. Chen	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
A systematic literature review on serious games evaluation: An application to software project management	Alejandro Calderón and Mercedes Ruiz	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Programming Fun(damentals): Using commercial video games to teach basic coding to adult learners	Joan Arnedo-Moreno and David García-Solórzano	2025	Science@Direct	Accepted
Tertiary students' acceptance of a game to teach information literacy	Yan Ru Guo and Dion Hoe-Lian Goh and Brendan Luyt	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Design for safety training for construction professionals: A digital game-based learning approach	Juliana Tay and Sufiana Safiena and Tianxiang Lan and Michelle SH Lim and Yang Miang Goh	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Application of serious games in chemical engineering courses	Ismael Díaz and Emilio J. González and María González-Miquel and Manuel Rodríguez	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
"What It Means to be a Digital Citizen": Using concept mapping and an educational game to explore children's conceptualization of digital citizenship	Jinping Zhong and Yunxiang Zheng	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Mindful learning: A mediator of mastery experience during digital creativity game-based learning among elementary school students	Yu-chu Yeh and Han-Lin Chang and Szu-Yu Chen	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Development and evaluation of a dynamic code visualization system for C programming education: The PVLS approach	Chien-Hung Lai and Pei-Wen Lin and Shu-Han You	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected

The Effectiveness of Serious Puzzle Games on Improving Introductory Learning of Computational Thinking Skills	Christopher Elroy Chandra and Jason Timothy and Dimas Ramdhan	2025	Science@Direct	Accepted
Conducting business disciplinary research by playing educational games: A case of the forecast sharing game in supply chain management	Yanzi Chen and Pi-Ying Yen and Yujie Zhang and Haoyu Liu	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Supporting learners in the transition from block-based to text-based programming, a systematic review	Glenn Strong and Nina Bresnihan and Brendan Tangney	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Evaluation of a Digital Game-Based Learning Program for Enhancing Youth Mental Health: A Structural Equation Modeling of the Program Effectiveness	Jenny MY Huen and Eliza SY Lai and Angie KY Shum and Sam WK So and Melissa KY Chan and Paul WC Wong and YW Law and Paul SF Yip	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
Overcoming illiteracy through game-based learning in refugee camps and urban slums	Lauri Pynnönen and Lauri Hietajärvi and Kristiina Kumpulainen and Lasse Lipponen	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
MR-LEAP: Mixed-Reality Learning Environment for Aspirational Programmers	Santiago Schez-Sobrino and Francisco M. García and Javier A. Albusac and Carlos Glez-Morcillo and Jose J. Castro-Schez and David Vallejo	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Interweaving gaming and educational technologies: Clustering and forecasting the trends of game-based learning research by bibliometric and visual analysis	Gwo-Jen Hwang and Pei-Ying Chen	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Fostering the Learning Process in a Programming Course With a Chatbot	Sohail Iqbal Malik and Mohammed Waseem Ashfaque and Roy Mathew and Jasiya Jabbar and Rim Salim Al-Nuaimi and Abir Alsideiri	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
AI-driven gamified speech training for primary students: framework and evaluation	Xing Sun and Zi-Xiang Xu and Ling-Chen Meng and Ding-Nan Shi	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
On the role of interaction mode and story structure in virtual reality serious games	Chris Ferguson and Egon L. {van den Broek} and Herre {van Oostendorp}	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
The use and impact of game-based learning on the learning experience and knowledge retention of nursing undergraduate students: A systematic literature review	Nuno Tavares	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Effect of theme game-based learning on psychiatric violence risk assessment and response knowledge, skills, and self-confidence of nursing students: A randomized controlled trial	Jinmei Zhao and Gang Zeng and Xinmiao Chen and Jiawei Huang and Zhichun Xia and Rongyu Liang and Thomas Wong and Yun Gao	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
How games for computing education are evaluated? A systematic literature review	Giani Petri and Christiane {Gresse von Wangenheim}	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Design of a Serious Game for Handling Obstetrical Emergencies	Estelle {Jean dit Gautier} and Virginie Bot-Robin and Aurélien Libessart and Guillaume Doucède and Michel Cosson and Chrystèle Rubod	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
Software-testing education: A systematic literature mapping	Vahid Garousi and Austen Rainer and Per Lauvås and Andrea Arcuri	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected

Like, tag and share: bolstering social media marketing to improve intention to visit a nature-based tourism destination	Vanessa Gaffar and Benny Tjahjono and Taufik Abdullah and Vidi Sukmayadi	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Expressing Disaster Situations for Evacuation Training Using Markerless Augmented Reality	Hiroyuki Mitsuhashi and Chie Tanimura and Junko Nemoto and Masami Shishibori	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
How is the use of technology in education evaluated? A systematic review	Jennifer W.M. Lai and Matt Bower	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effect of simulation games on the learning of computational problem solving	Chen-Chung Liu and Yuan-Bang Cheng and Chia-Wen Huang	2011	Science@Direct	Accepted
A systematic mapping study on teaching and learning Computational Thinking through programming in higher education	Christina Tikva and Efthimios Tambouris	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Effects of experiential service learning in improving community engagement perception, sustainability awareness, and data analytics competency	W. Eric Lee and Arif Perdana	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Blended Learning Approach:	Su Ting Yong and Kung Ming Tiong	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Recommendation web service for choosing an individual educational path in the field of transportation systems' programming	Igor Kotsyuba and Alexey Shikov and Kirill Karpik and Mikhail Galperin and Aleksandr Kudriashov and Julia Silko	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Does Physical Activity Enhance Learning Performance?: Learning Effectiveness of Game-based Experiential Learning for University Library Instruction	Kosuke Kaneko and Yuriko Saito and Yukari Nohara and Eriko Kudo and Masanori Yamada	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Fabricating concepts: using custom 3D models to teach abstract concepts	Jon McNaughtan and Ryan Litsey and Nichole Morelock	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
BlockTrainHK: An online learning game for experiencing blockchain concepts	Yung Po Tsang and Chun Ho Wu and Carman Ka Man Lee	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Exploring the future of startup leadership development	Lisa Prommer and Victor Tiberius and Sascha Kraus	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Gamification and e-learning for young learners: A systematic literature review, bibliometric analysis, and future research agenda	Abhishek Behl and Nirma Jayawardena and Vijay Pereira and Nazrul Islam and Manlio Del Giudice and Jyoti Choudrie	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Use of a simulation game in delivering blended lifelong learning in the construction industry – Opportunities and Challenges	John Wall and Vian Ahmed	2008	Science@Direct	Rejected
How to learn and how to teach computational thinking: Suggestions based on a review of the literature	Ting-Chia Hsu and Shao-Chen Chang and Yu-Ting Hung	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Improving programming skills in engineering education through problem-based game projects with Scratch	Damla Topalli and Nergiz Ercil Cagiltay	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Effects of Robotics Programming on Enhancing Computational Thinking Among Middle School Students in Saudi Arabia	Wafa Ahmad Alalawi and Mohd Nihra Haruzuan Bin Mohamad Said and Mohd Fadzil Bin Abdul Hanid	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Creative thinking in digital game design and development: A case study	Cesar C. Navarrete	2013	Science@Direct	Rejected

A meta-analysis on the effect of technology on the achievement of less advantaged students	Giorgio {Di Pietro} and Jonatan {Castaño Muñoz}	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
An implementation of design-based learning through creating educational computer games: A case study on mathematics learning during design and computing	Fengfeng Ke	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
Developing enrollment intentions for work-based learning that uses artificial intelligence (AI): aspects for marketing interventions for higher education institutions	Eiman Negm	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
A narrative literature review of games, animations and simulations to teach research methods and statistics	Elizabeth A. Boyle and Ewan W. MacArthur and Thomas M. Connolly and Thomas Hainey and Madalina Manea and Anne Kärki and Peter {van Rosmalen}	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
A framework for understanding game-based teaching and learning	Jeffrey B. Holmes and Elisabeth R. Gee	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
A systematic review of immersive virtual reality applications for higher education: Design elements, lessons learned, and research agenda	Jaziar Radianti and Tim A. Majchrzak and Jennifer Fromm and Isabell Wohlgenannt	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Gamification of Computer Programming Tasks to Promote the Growth Mind-Set in a Disadvantaged School	Garry Gorman and Nigel McKelvey and Thomas Dowling	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effects of programming interventions in early childhood: A meta-analysis	Bianca A. Simonsmeier and Kristin Kampmann and Jacqueline Staub and Ronny Scherer	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Future-ready instructional technology for early childhood education: a bibliometric and meta-synthesis analysis	Muh {Asriadi AM} and Mirawati Mirawati and Ayu Hopiani and Ririn Despriliani	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Children's engagement with digital technology in educational spaces: A scoping review	Jacquelyn Harverson and Chris Zomer and Celine Chu and Sharon Horwood and Marcus Horwood and Maria Nicholas and Louise Paatsch	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Game4NurseSupervisor: Development of a board game for nursing mentoring	Inês Santos Almeida and Cristina Pinto and Andreia Lima and Teresa Moreira and Carla Sílvia Fernandes	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
The impact of gamification on learning and instruction: A systematic review of empirical evidence	Zamzami Zainuddin and Samuel Kai Wah Chu and Muhammad Shujahat and Corinne Jacqueline Perera	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Mi Superpoder es la Programación: A tool for teaching programming to children and youth	Erika J. {Gutiérrez Beltrán} and Juan C. {Martínez Arias}	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Detecting latent topics and trends in educational technologies over four decades using structural topic modeling: A retrospective of all volumes of Computers & Education	Xieling Chen and Di Zou and Gary Cheng and Haoran Xie	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Evaluation of a Web-Based Social Network Electronic Game in Enhancing Mental Health Literacy for Young People	Tim MH Li and Michael Chau and Paul WC Wong and Eliza SY Lai and Paul SF Yip	2013	Science@Direct	Rejected

The Development of a Gamebook for Education	Mauro Figueiredo and José Bidarra	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
How block-based, text-based, and hybrid block/text modalities shape novice programming practices	David Weintrop and Uri Wilensky	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Bibliometric mapping of mobile learning	Idris Goksu	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Cloud-assisted gamification for education and learning – Recent advances and challenges	Saqib Hakak and Nurul Fazmidar Mohd Noor and Mohamad Nizam Ayub and Hannyzurra Affal and Nornazlita Hussin and Ejaz ahmed and Muhammad Imran	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
“Move over, I will find Jerusalem”: Artifacts in game design in classrooms	Kristine Øygardslia and Pål Aarsand	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Moving school-based CSA prevention education online: Advantages and challenges of the “new normal”	Melissa A. Bright and Diana Ortega and David Finkelhor and Kerryann Walsh	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
The influence of the level of free-choice learning activities on the use of an educational computer game	Wolmet Barendregt and Tilde M. Bekker	2011	Science@Direct	Rejected
Out-of-school assistance in the teaching of visual creative programming in the game-based environment – Case study: Poland	Taras Panskyi and Zdzislawa Rowinska and Sebastian Biedron	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Design of online teaching interaction mode for vocational education based on gamified-learning	Zhongbao Ma and Wei Li	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Mars mission program for primary students: Building student and teacher skills in science, technology, engineering and mathematics	Naomi Mathers and Michael Pakakis and Ian Christie	2011	Science@Direct	Rejected
Flow in ChatGPT-based logic learning and its influences on logic and self-efficacy in English argumentative writing	Ruofei Zhang and Di Zou and Gary Cheng and Haoran Xie	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Designing and evaluating a high interactive augmented reality system for programming learning	Gloria {Yi-Ming Kao} and Cheng-An Ruan	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Exploring Gamified Computer-Assisted Instruction in College English Vocabulary Teaching	Yi Tan	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Computer science education and K-12 students’ computational thinking: A systematic review	Sang Joon Lee and Gregory M. Francom and Jeremiah Nuatomue	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
A gamified app on emotion recognition and anger management for pre-school children	Iolie Nicolaidou and Federica Tozzi and Athos Antoniadis	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Impact of Gamification Elements on Live Streaming E-Commerce (Live Commerce)	Fayola Fayola and Vanessa Graciela and Vivian Chandra and Dyah Wahyu Sukmaningsih	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Ten years of augmented reality in education: A meta-analysis of (quasi-) experimental studies to investigate the impact	Hsin-Yi Chang and Theerapong Binali and Jyh-Chong Liang and Guo-Li Chiou and Kun-Hung Cheng and Silvia Wen-Yu Lee and Chin-Chung Tsai	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Quest for the Golden Rule: An effective social skills promotion and bullying prevention program	Alice Rubin-Vaughan and Debra Pepler and Steven Brown and Wendy Craig	2011	Science@Direct	Rejected

A Systematic Review of Student Engagement Research in Adaptive Learning Platforms	Patricia D. Simon and Lily Min Zeng and Luke K. Fryer	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effect of disaster preparedness training programs on nurses' readiness and competence: a systematic review of randomized controlled trials	Gürkan Özden	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effects of integrating mobile devices with teaching and learning on students' learning performance: A meta-analysis and research synthesis	Yao-Ting Sung and Kuo-En Chang and Tzu-Chien Liu	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
Identifying emerging trends for implementing learning technology in special education: A state-of-the-art review of selected articles published in 2008–2012	Gi-Zen Liu and No-Wei Wu and Yi-Wen Chen	2013	Science@Direct	Rejected
Designing AI-powered user-centric platforms for energy consumption and carbon footprint reduction	Daniel Chwaifo Malann and Ayomide Titus Ogungbemi and Great Iruoghene Edo and Ali B.M. Ali and Agatha Ngukuran Jikah and Emad Yousif and Uwadia Francis and Ufuoma Augustina Igbuku and Ephraim Evi Alex Oghoro and Arthur Efeoghene Athan Essaghah and Dina S. Ahmed and Maryam Rabi Aliyu and Huzaifa Umar and Ahmed A. Alamiery	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Human-centred learning analytics and AI in education: A systematic literature review	Riordan Alfredo and Vanessa Echeverria and Yueqiao Jin and Lixiang Yan and Zachari Swiecki and Dragan Gašević and Roberto Martinez-Maldonado	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
What's in a Name? Clarifying the Nomenclature of Virtual Simulation	Robyn Cant and Simon Cooper and Roland Sussex and Fiona Bogossian	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
A psychological intervention reduces doping likelihood in Italian athletes: A replication and extension	Maria Kavussanu and Enrico Rubaltelli and Irene Leo and Philip Hurst and Marta Giovannoni and Vassilis Barkoukis and Fabio Lucidi and Simone D'Ambrogio and Christopher Ring	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
'Lots done, more to do': The current state of interaction design and children research and future directions	Michail Giannakos and Panos Markopoulos and Juan Pablo Hourcade and Alissa N. Antle	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Managing the future of talents: digital innovation in learning organizations	Teresa Galanti and Stefania Fantinelli	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Randomized control trial in nursing education: A bibliometric analysis and visualization	Esin Ateş and Ebru Konal Korkmaz	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
The e-learning persuasion through gamification: an elaboration likelihood model perspective	Nirma Sadamali Jayawardena	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Multidimensional Talent Cultivation Method of College Art and Design Majors From the Perspective of Artificial Intelligence	Peng Wang	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected

Interleaved practice in physics benefits from collaboration	Maria Danzglock and Roland Berger and Martin Hänze	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Patient Safety Elements Taught to Preregistration Nurses Using Simulation Designs: An Integrative Review	Colleen Ryan and Chanchal Kurup and Robyn Cant and Kerry Reid-Searl and Trish Johnson and Melanie Barlow and Leeanne Heaton	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Advanced multimedia engineering education in energy, process integration and optimisation	Jiří Jaromír Klimeš and Zdravko Kravanja and Petar Sabev Varbanov and Hon Loong Lam	2013	Science@Direct	Rejected
RETRACTED: Integrating AI-based adaptive learning into the flipped classroom model to enhance engagement and learning outcomes	Jozsef Katona and Klara Ida Katonane Gyonyoru	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Simulation in a blended learning curriculum for neonatology	Catherine L. Chang and Nicolle Fernández Dyess and Lindsay C. Johnston	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Facilitating computational thinking with AI: A three-level meta-analytic evidence for future-ready learning	Yuru Lin and Yi Zhang and Yuqin Yang and Shidan Pan and Xu Ren and Dengkang Chen	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Foster employability and fight social exclusion through the development of lifelong learning (LLL) key-competences: reviewing twenty years of LLL policies	Andrea Ceschi and Marco Perini and Andrea Scalco and Monica Pentassuglia and Elisa Righetti and Beniamino Caputo	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Nursing students' learning experiences, outcomes, and methods in distance education: An integrative literature review	Petra Nissinen and Marja Silén-Lipponen and Outi Kähkönen and Terhi Saaranen	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Learning academic vocabulary with digital flashcards: Comparing the outcomes from computers and smartphones	Zahra Zarrati and Mohammad Zohrabi and Hakimeh Abedini and Ismail Xodabande	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Virtual Clinical Simulation Adoption and Use by Licensed Practical Nurse/Licensed Vocational Nurse Education Programs During the COVID-19 Pandemic	Nicole Kaminski-Ozturk and Brendan Martin	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Fostering learning beyond urban experiment boundaries	E.-(Els) Beukers and L.-(Luca) Bertolini	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Exploring an approach based on digital games for teaching programming concepts to young children	Tancicleide Carina {Simões Gomes} and Taciana {Pontual Falcão} and Patrícia {Cabral de Azevedo Restelli Tedesco}	2018	Science@Direct	Accepted
Supporting Adaptive English Learning With Fuzzy Logic-Based Personalized Learning	Fangfang Ding	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected

Learning factories for future oriented research and education in manufacturing	Eberhard Abele and George Chryssolouris and Wilfried Sihn and Joachim Metternich and Hoda ElMaraghy and Günther Seliger and Gunilla Sivard and Waguih ElMaraghy and Vera Hummel and Michael Tisch and Stefan Seifermann	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Participatory design and participatory debugging: Listening to students to improve computational thinking by creating games	Anastasios Theodoropoulos	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
A scoping review of technological tools for supporting victims of online sexual harassment	Yuying Tan and Heidi Vandebosch and Sara Pabian and Karolien Poels	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Sports game teaching and high precision sports training system based on virtual reality technology	Yang Pan	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Simulation-games for Learning Conducive Workplaces: A Case Study for Manual Assembly	Bastian C. Müller and Carsten Reise and Bui Minh Duc and Günther Seliger	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
The application of educational technology to develop problem-solving skills: A systematic review	Dan Lu and Ya-Nan Xie	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
From networked students centrality to student networks density: What really matters for student performance?	Kristel Vignery	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Utilization, application and effectiveness of metaverse in simulation-based nursing education: A systematic review	Carley Jans and Cherie Lucas and Tracy Levett-Jones	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Challenges and opportunities for educating health professionals after the COVID-19 pandemic	Julio Frenk and Lincoln C Chen and Latha Chandran and Elizabeth O H Groff and Roderick King and Afaf Meleis and Harvey V Fineberg	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
A BIBLIOMETRIC AND CONTENT ANALYSIS OF CRITICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY EDUCATION	Ayten Aktoprak and Cigdem Hursen	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
The use of virtual reality in patient education related to medical somatic treatment: A scoping review	Marijke {van der Linde-van den Bor} and Fiona Slond and Omayra C.D. Liesdek and Willem J. Suyker and Saskia W.M. Weldam	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Effectiveness of Telehealth Interventions on Cognitive Function and Quality of Life in Adults With Neurological Disorders: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis	Yule Hu and Yan Li and Jiaying Li and Justina Yat Wa Liu and Sylvia M. Gustin and Mengqi Li and Angela Yee Man Leung	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Toy user interface design—Tools for Child–Computer Interaction	Anna Priscilla {de Albuquerque Wheler} and Judith Kelner and Patrick C.K. Hung and Bruno de Souza Jeronimo and Railton da Silva Rocha and Aluizio Fausto Ribeiro Araújo	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
A review of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on pre-registration medical radiation science education	C.K.C. Ng	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected

Learning for Low Carbon Living: The Potential of Mobile Learning Applications for Built Environment Trades and Professionals in Australia	Tomi Winfree and Paul Goldacre and Mohammadhossein Sherkat and Peter Graham and Antonette Mendoza and Tim Miller	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Theorizing STEM Leadership: Agency, Identity and Community	Uma Natarajan and Aik Ling Tan and Tang Wee Teo	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
The cybersecurity mesh: A comprehensive survey of involved artificial intelligence methods, cryptographic protocols and challenges for future research	Bruno Ramos-Cruz and Javier Andreu-Perez and Luis Martínez	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Profile Outline of Higher Education E-Tutoring Programs for the Digital-Native Student – Literature Review	Iulia A. Copaci and Alina S. Rusu	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Digital Health Professions Education on Diabetes Management: Systematic Review by the Digital Health Education Collaboration	Zhilian Huang and Monika Semwal and Shuen Yee Lee and Mervin Tee and William Ong and Woan Shin Tan and Ram Bajpai and Lorraine {Tudor Car}	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Hybrid learning style identification and developing adaptive problem-solving learning activities	Yu Hsin Hung and Ray I. Chang and Chun Fu Lin	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
Representation of Events and Rules in Gamification Systems	Jakub Swacha	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Feasibility of tracking laparoscopic instruments in a box trainer using a Leap Motion Controller	I. Oropesa and T.L. {de Jong} and P. Sánchez-González and J. Dankelman and E.J. Gómez	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
Developing a problem-solving learning system to assess the effects of different materials on learning performance and attitudes	Chun Fu Lin and Yu Hsin Hung and Ray I. Chang and Shih Hao Hung	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
Simulation-based teaching in critical care, anaesthesia and emergency medicine	Erwan L'Her and Thomas Geeraerts and Jean-Philippe Desclefs and Dan Benhamou and Antonia Blanié and Charles Cerf and Véronique Delmas and Mercedes Jourdain and François Lecomte and Islem Ouanes and Marc Garnier and Chirine Mossadegh	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Simulation in the Internet age: The place of Web-based simulation in nursing education. An integrative review	Robyn P. Cant and Simon J. Cooper	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
The role of neurofeedback games in enhancing cognitive abilities during physical education lessons	Yun Bo Wang and Zhen Mei Yao and Gao Hua Zhang	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Understanding information practices through video-based research: Opportunities and challenges of collecting researcher-generated and participant-generated video data	Soo Hyeon Kim and Gi Woong Choi	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effectiveness of the virtual patient-based social learning approach in undergraduate nursing education: A quasi-experimental study	Gwo-Jen Hwang and Ching-Yi Chang and Hiroaki Ogata	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Effects of digital interventions on neuroplasticity and brain function of individuals with developmental disabilities: A systematic review	Hyunyoung Lee and Yoomi Shin and Hayoung Moon and Yuna Choi and Anna Lee	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected

A systematic review of construction skills acquisition in higher education institutions	Olubimbola Oladimeji and Assed Naked Haddad	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Virtual reality in English language education: A systematic review of opportunities and challenges in higher education	I. Wayan Eka Dian Rahmanu and Gyöngyvér Molnár	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Environmental correlates of early language and literacy in low- to middle-income Filipino families	Katrina May Dulay and Sum Kwing Cheung and Catherine McBride	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
An innovative talent training mechanism for maker education in colleges and universities based on the IPSO-BP-enabled technique	Yuanbing Liu	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Review and analysis of research on Video Games and Artificial Intelligence: a look back and a step forward	João Paulo Sousa and Rogério Tavares and João Pedro Gomes and Vitor Mendonça	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Value trace problems with assisting references for Python programming self-study	San Hay Mar {Hay Mar Shwe} and Nobuo Funabiki and Yan Watequlis Syaifudin and Phyu Phyu Tar and Htoo Htoo Sandi Kyaw and Hnin Aye Thant and Wen-Chung Kao and Nandar Win Min and Thandar Myint and Ei Ei Htet	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Information Literacy: Making Asynchronous Learning More Effective With Best Practices That Include Humor	Debby R. Wegener	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Simulation Training in the ICU	Nitin Seam and Ai Jin Lee and Megan Vennero and Lillian Emler	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Mobile Learning Framework for Lifelong Learning	Norazah Nordin and Mohamed Amin Embi and Melor Md. Yunus	2010	Science@Direct	Rejected
The importance/role of education in chemical engineering	Meyer Th. and E. Schaer and J. Abildskov and H. Feise and J. Glassey and M. Liauw and C. Ó'Súilleabháin and M. Wilk	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Healthcare Interventions for Children Using Nonimmersive Virtual Reality: A Mixed Methods Systematic Review	Hyeseon Yun and Mina Park and Hooyun Lee and Eun Kyoung Choi	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Assessing the emotional impact of virtual reality-based teacher training	Kalliopi Evangelia Stavroulia and Maria Christofi and Evangelia Baka and Despina Michael-Grigoriou and Nadia Magnenat-Thalman and Andreas Lanitis	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Revolutionizing HRM: a review of human-robot collaboration in HRM functions and the imperative of change readiness	Sehrish Shahid and Kuldeep Kaur and Syed Mofazzal Mohyuddin and Verma Prikshat and Parth Patel	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
How secondary school girls perceive Computational Thinking practices through collaborative programming with the micro:bit	Mojtaba Shahin and Christabel Gonsalvez and Jon Whittle and Chunyang Chen and Li Li and Xin Xia	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected

Usage of augmented reality (AR) and development of e-learning outcomes: An empirical evaluation of students' e-learning experience	Abdullah M. Baabdullah and Abdullellah A. Alsulaimani and Alhasan Allamnakhrah and Ali Abdallah Alalwan and Yogesh K. Dwivedi and Nripendra P. Rana	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Employer development of professional capabilities among early career workers and implications for the design of work-based learning	Denise Jackson and Hairong Shan and Stephanie Meek	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
AI & learning: A preferred future	Venkat Srinivasan	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Thematic evolution of smart learning environments, insights and directions from a 20-year research milestones: A bibliometric analysis	Della Maulidiya and Budi Nugroho and Harry B. Santoso and Zainal A. Hasibuan	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Internet of Things for education: A smart and secure system for schools monitoring and alerting	Kashif Naseer Qureshi and Ayesha Naveed and Yamna Kashif and Gwanggil Jeon	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Learning-to-learn sand cone model integrated lean learning framework for construction industry	Agana Parameswaran and K.A.T.O. Ranadewa	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
The meaning and application of student-centered learning in nursing education: An integrative review of the literature	Eva Berg and Margret Lepp	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Editor's choice 2006: Selected online learning resources	Laurie P. Dringus	2006	Science@Direct	Rejected
Reprint: Learning with a strategic management simulation game: A case study	Mark Loon and Jason Evans and Clive Kerridge	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Integration of environmental sustainability considerations within architectural programmes in higher education: A review of teaching and implementation approaches	Paola Boarin and Antonio Martinez-Molina	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
The role of national cybersecurity strategies on the improvement of cybersecurity education	Saleh AIDaajeh and Heba Saleous and Saed Alrabaee and Ezedin Barka and Frank Breitingger and Kim-Kwang {Raymond Choo}	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Toy user interfaces: Systematic and industrial mapping	Anna Priscilla {de Albuquerque} and Judith Kelner	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Unplugged activities in the elementary school mathematics classroom: The effects on students' computational thinking and mathematical creativity	Linlin Hu and Hao Wang	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Conducting Online Lab Experiments with Blockly	Daniel Galan and Ruben Heradio and Luis {de la Torre} and Sebastian Dormido and Francisco Esquembre	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Educating a world on the move: rethinking teacher preparation in the context of mass global migration and increasingly diverse classrooms	A. Lin Goodwin and Seung Eun McDevitt and Crystal Chen Lee and Sibel Akin-Sabuncu	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected

Evaluating Aspects of Usability in Video Game-Based Programming Learning Platforms	Jaime Díaz and Jeferson Arango López and Samuel Sepúlveda and Gabriel Mauricio {Ramírez Villegas} and Danay Ahumada and Fernando Moreira	2021	Science@Direct	Accepted
A comparative analysis of campus greening practices at universities in Romania and Bulgaria: Sharing the same challenges?	Mihaela Sima and Ines Grigorescu and Dan Bălteanu and Mariyana Nikolova	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
The Development of an e-platform to Strengthen Nursing in Kazakhstan: A Systematic Review and a Delphi Study to Define Requirements	Bea Dijkman and Alberta Oosterhoff and Amangali Akanov and Wolter Paans	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Learning activities in bachelor nursing education to learn pre- and postoperative nursing care—A scoping review	Eva Mari Andreassen and Åshild Slettebø and Anne Opsal	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Maintaining older brain functionality: A targeted review	Soledad Ballesteros and Eduard Kraft and Silvina Santana and Chariklia Tziraki	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Diverse approaches to learning with immersive Virtual Reality identified from a systematic review	Mihye Won and Dewi Ayu Kencana Ungu and Henry Matovu and David F. Treagust and Chin-Chung Tsai and Jungho Park and Mauro Mocerino and Roy Tasker	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Fun in Making: Understanding the experience of fun and learning through curriculum-based Making in the elementary school classroom	Sharon Lynn Chu and Genna Angello and Michael Saenz and Francis Quek	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Developing students' digital competences through collaborative game design	Noora L. Laakso and Tiina S. Korhonen and Kai P.J. Hakkarainen	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
A review of Project-Based Learning (PBL) and Computational Thinking (CT) in teaching and learning	Aslina Saad and Suhaila Zainudin	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
The role of motivation, ability, and opportunity in university teachers' continuance use intention for flipped teaching	Hui-Min Lai and Yu-Lin Hsiao and Pi-Jung Hsieh	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
The integration of immersive virtual reality in tertiary nursing and midwifery education: A scoping review	Shanna Fealy and Donovan Jones and Alison Hutton and Kristen Graham and Liz McNeill and Linda Sweet and Michael Hazelton	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
E-learning enhancement through educational data mining with Covid-19 outbreak period in backdrop: A review	Kudratdeep Aulakh and Rajendra Kumar Roul and Manisha Kaushal	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Analyzing augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) recent development in education	Abdullah M. Al-Ansi and Mohammed Jabooob and Askar Garad and Ahmed Al-Ansi	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Development and Evaluation of Digital Game-Based Training for Managers to Promote Employee Mental Health and Reduce Mental Illness Stigma at Work: Quasi-Experimental Study of Program Effectiveness	Sabine Elisabeth Hanisch and Ulrich Walter Birner and Cornelia Oberhauser and Dennis Nowak and Carla Sabariego	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Facilitating student engagement through the flipped learning approach in K-12: A systematic review	Melissa Bond	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected

Digital creativity: Research themes and framework	Maria R. Lee and Tsung Teng Chen	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Affective computing in education: A systematic review and future research	Elaheh Yadegaridehkordi and Nurul Fazmidar Binti Mohd Noor and Mohamad Nizam Bin Ayub and Hannyzzura Binti Affal and Nornazlita Binti Hussin	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Nudging in education	Mette Trier Damgaard and Helena Skyt Nielsen	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Self-regulated learning strategies & academic achievement in online higher education learning environments: A systematic review	J. Broadbent and W.L. Poon	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Interdisciplinary innovation: psychoeducational multimedia technologies	Larisa V. Shavinina	1998	Science@Direct	Rejected
Studying interrelations of computational thinking and creativity: A scoping review (2011–2020)	Rotem Israel-Fishelson and Arnon Hershkovitz	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Emerging Technologies	Gretchen M. Carrasquillo-Ramos	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Teachers' Perception Related to the Promotion of Nanotechnology Concepts in Romanian Science Education	Laura Monica Gorghiu and Gabriel Gorghiu	2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
eGames: Is imagination the forgotten ingredient?	Tom Benjamin	2010	Science@Direct	Rejected
At the boundary of school: Continuity and discontinuity in learning across contexts	Larika H. Bronkhorst and Sanne F. Akkerman	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 10 - Designing the Intel-Powered Classmate PC	Jose {Ramon Morales Avalos}	2009	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 7 - Disruptive Technologies Affecting Education and Their Implications for Curricular Redesign	C. Donald Combs and Bertalan Meskó	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 11 - Animated Pedagogical Agents and Emotion	Enilda Romero-Hall	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
Secondary school students' mental models and attitudes regarding artificial intelligence - A scoping review	Erik Marx and Thiemo Leonhardt and Nadine Bergner	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Information flow and cognition affect each other: Evidence from digital learning	Kshitij Sharma and Katerina Mangaroska and Niels van Berkel and Michail Giannakos and Vassilis Kostakos	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Effect of a Technology-Integrated Curriculum on Sugary Drink and Snack Intake of Elementary-Aged Youth Experiencing Low Income	Kate Balestracci and Linda Sebelia and Geoffrey Greene and Adam Moore and Grayson Baird and Kelsi Chappell and Alison Tovar	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Teaching Programming in the Higher Education not for Engineering Students	Gabor Kiss	2013	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 3 - Raising Intelligence by Means of Behavioral Training	Norbert Jaušovec and Anja Pahor	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected

Inclusion by design: Embedding inclusive teaching practice into design and preparation of laboratory classes	Ellen Hackl and Irina Ermolina	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Talk to me personally: Personalization of language style in computer-based learning	Maria Reichelt and Frauke Kämmerer and Helmut M. Niegemann and Steffi Zander	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
Artificial intelligence and its impact on the current and future transport workforce: policies and research to bridge the gaps and foster cooperation versus competition between countries	Cristina Pronello	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Multimedia learning systems: a future interactive educational tool	Andy Lock Yen Low and Kevin Lock Teng Low and Voon Chet Koo	2003	Science@Direct	Rejected
Money adventures: Introducing economic concepts to preschool children in the South African context	V. Roos and P. Chiroro and C. {van Coppenhagen} and I. Smith and E. {van Heerden} and R.E. Abdoola and K. Robertson and C. Beukes	2005	Science@Direct	Rejected
Computational thinking in early childhood education: Reviewing the literature and redeveloping the three-dimensional framework	Yue Zeng and Weipeng Yang and Alfredo Bautista	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Inscript: A courseware specification language	Rob Koper	1991	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 1 - Investing in early childhood development in preschool and at home	Greg Duncan and Ariel Kalil and Magne Mogstad and Mari Rege	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
End-user development, end-user programming and end-user software engineering: A systematic mapping study	Barbara Rita Barricelli and Fabio Cassano and Daniela Fogli and Antonio Piccinno	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Anticipatory Guidance Preferences of Latina Migrant Farmworker Mothers	Jill F. Kilanowski	2013	Science@Direct	Rejected
Investigating Context Awareness of Affective Computing Systems: A Critical Approach	Aggeliki Vlachostergiou and George Caridakis and Stefanos Kollias	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
Positive youth development linked with prevention in a Vietnamese American community: Successes, challenges, and lessons learned	Michelle C. Kegler and Kai H. Young and LaDonna Marshall and Dong Bui and Sharon Rodine	2005	Science@Direct	Rejected
Subject Index (By Abstract Number)		2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Research and Education Poster Abstracts Presented at the 123rd Annual Meeting of the American Association of Colleges of Pharmacy, July 23-27, 2022		2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Symposiums		2013	Science@Direct	Rejected
Index		2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
119th Annual Meeting of the American Association of Colleges of Pharmacy, Boston, Massachusetts, July 21-25, 2018		2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Research and Education Poster Abstracts Presented at the 122nd Virtual Annual Meeting of the American Association of Colleges of Pharmacy, July 19-22, 2021		2021	Science@Direct	Rejected

1 - Overview of recent innovation	Kirstie Nicholson	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
An Empirical Investigation on the Benefits of Gamification in Programming Courses	Marín, B. and Frez, J. and Cruz-Lemus, J. and Genero, M.	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Code hunt: searching for secret code for fun	Tillmann, Nikolai and Bishop, Judith and Horspool, Nigel and Perelman, Daniel and Xie, Tao	2014	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Beyond Programming: A Computer-Based Assessment of Computational Thinking Competency	Lai, Rina P. Y.	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Evaluation of the user experience and intrinsic motivation with educational and mainstream digital games	de Lima, Luis Gustavo Rotoly and de Lima Salgado, André and Freire, André Pimenta	2015	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Augmented Reality and Robotics: A Survey and Taxonomy for AR-enhanced Human-Robot Interaction and Robotic Interfaces	Suzuki, Ryo and Karim, Adnan and Xia, Tian and Hedayati, Hooman and Marquardt, Nicolai	2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
A Multi-level Analysis of the Relationship between Instructional Practices and Retention in Computer Science	Peteranetz, Markeya S. and Soh, Leen-Kiat	2020	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
If Memory Serves: Towards Designing and Evaluating a Game for Teaching Pointers to Undergraduate Students	McGill, Monica M. and Johnson, Chris and Atlas, James and Bouchard, Durell and Messom, Chris and Pollock, Ian and Scott, Michael James	2018	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
The Spread and Impact of Game Innovations: A Systematic Review of Academic and Applied Domains	Steinkuehler, Constance and Squire, Kurt	2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Analyzing Students' Learning Engagements Using PLS-SEM: A Case Study in A Small Private Online Programming Course	Daramsenge, Bilegjargal and Hsueh, Nien-Lin and Lai, Lien-Chi	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
A TUI-based Programming Tool for Children	Wang, Danli and Zhang, Lan and Qi, Yunfeng and Sun, Fang	2015	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Evidence for Teaching Practices that Broaden Participation for Women in Computing	Morrison, Briana B. and Quinn, Beth A. and Bradley, Steven and Buffardi, Kevin and Harrington, Brian and Hu, Helen H. and Kallia, Maria and McNeill, Fiona and Ola, Oluwakemi and Parker, Miranda and Rosato, Jennifer and Waite, Jane	2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Understanding Fun in Learning to Code: A Multi-Modal Data approach	Tisza, Gabriella and Sharma, Kshitij and Papavlasopoulou, Sofia and Markopoulos, Panos and Giannakos, Michail	2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Pulling your weight? New CS entrants' reflections on their experience of collaborative work at high school	Bhardwaj, Jyoti	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Teaching AI to K-12 Learners: Lessons, Issues, and Guidance	Grover, Shuchi	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Comparing Block-Based and Text-Based Programming in High School Computer Science Classrooms	Weintrop, David and Wilensky, Uri	2017	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Making the Transition to Text-Based Programming: The Pilot Evaluation of a Computational Thinking Intervention for Primary School Students	Kunz, Katrin and Moeller, Korbinian and Ninaus, Manuel and Trautwein, Ulrich and Tsarava, Katerina	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Innovative application of gamification teaching in high school information technology courses	Li, Yu-Guo and Liu, Yi-Ze	2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Teaching Accessibility: A Family Workshop for Middle School Students	Liu, Chunyu and Wang, Annie and Iyer, Mithali and Slaughter, Gwendolyn and Bosch, Allie and Lodvikov, Elizabeth and Zhou, Kyrie Zhixuan and Kletenik, Devorah and Adler, Rachel F.	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Autonomy-supportive game benefits both inexperienced and experienced programmers	Lee, Michael J. and Shen, Ruiqi	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Cyberspace meets brick and mortar: an investigation into how students engage in peer to peer feedback using both cyberlearning and physical infrastructures	Basawapatna, Ashok R. and Repenning, Alexander	2010	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Parsons Problems and Beyond: Systematic Literature Review and Empirical Study Designs	Ericson, Barbara J. and Denny, Paul and Prather, James and Duran, Rodrigo and Hellas, Arto and Leinonen, Juho and Miller, Craig S. and Morrison, Briana B. and Pearce, Janice L. and Rodger, Susan H.	2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Intrinsic vs. Extrinsic Programming Challenges in Educational Games: How they shape Children's Computational Thinking, Learning Drive, and Game Engagement	Chen, Baijun and Pan, Yushan and Xiang, Nan and Huang, Shenze Shandel	2026	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Applying a Blended Board Game System with Robotic Arm for Training Computational Thinking: Learning through Human-Machine Competition	Yong, Lin and Zhan, Zehui and Zou, Xuanxuan and Chen, Li and Lin, Zhihang and Zhan, Weiyu	2023	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
In-game assessments increase novice programmers' engagement and level completion speed	Lee, Michael J. and Ko, Amy J. and Kwan, Irwin	2013	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Cyber Gamification: Implementing Gamified Adaptive Learning Environments for Effective Cyber Security Teams Education	Alothman, Basil Yousef	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Integrating Serious and Casual Game Design Approaches: A Framework for Activist-Casual Game Design	King, Daniel	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Making university education more like middle school computer club: facilitating the flow of inspiration	Repenning, Alexander and Basawapatna, Ashok and Koh, Kyu Han	2009	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Comparative Analysis of Gender Differences in Expectations and Value Perceptions Regarding the Spread of AI Robots	Kanoh, Hiroko	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Comparing the Effectiveness of Online Learning Approaches on CS1 Learning Outcomes	Lee, Michael J. and Ko, Amy J.	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Knowledge assessment: game for assessment of symptoms of child physical abuse	Zhao, Richard and Shelton, Christopher R. and Hetzel-Riggin, Melanie D. and LaRiccia, Jordan and Louchart, Gregory and Meanor, Adam and Risser, Heather J.	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Towards an Educational Computing Career Exploration Game	Kao, Dominic and Magana, Alejandra J. and Oyedokun, Olaoluwa and Ravi, Akash	2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
FOES Sparking Programming Interest in Non-IT Students Through a JavaScript Fighting Game	Shaklee, Alex and Burns, Alec and Jin, Wei and Xu, Xin	2023	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Essential Aspects in Digital Educational Games to Support the Teaching-Learning of Computing Contents	Zimbrão, Rafael De Oliveira and Oliveira, Alessandra Marta De and Oliveira, Edmar Wellington and Valle, Pedro Henrique Dias	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
The Students' Perspective on Computational Thinking through Flipped Classroom in K-12 Programming Course	Choi, Wan Chong and Chang, Chi In	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Teaching how to program using automated assessment and functional glossy games (experience report)	Almeida, Josê Bacelar and Cunha, Alcino and Macedo, Nuno and Pacheco, Hugo and Proença, Josê	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Innovate in your program computer class: an approach based on a serious game	Piteira, Martinha and Haddad, Samir R.	2011	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
ENGAGE: A Game-based Learning Environment for Middle School Computational Thinking	Boyer, Kristy and Buffum, Philip Sheridan and Culbertson, Kirby and Frankosky, Megan and Lester, James and Martinez-Arocho, Allison and Min, Wookhee and Mott, Bradford and Rodriguez, Fernando and Wiebe, Eric	2015	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Computational thinking and practice: a generic approach to computing in Danish high schools	Caspersen, Michael E. and Nowack, Palle	2013	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Assembler's Adventure in Sands: A Narrative Puzzle Game for Learning Assembly Logic and Computational Thinking	Leal, Robert Hortua and Imran, Hazra	2025	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Design Insights into the Creation and Evaluation of a Computer Science Educational Game	Horn, Britton and Clark, Christopher and Strom, Oskar and Chao, Hilery and Stahl, Amy J. and Hartevelde, Casper and Smith, Gillian	2016	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Leveling up Learning: Serious Games for Computing Education - Long-Term Opportunities and Risks	Wünsche, Burkhard Claus and Hooper, Steffan and Whalley, Jacqueline and Straand, Ingjerd and Denny, Paul and Crow, Tyne and Lange-Nawka, Dominik and Luxton-Reilly, Andrew and Thompson, Samuel E. R.	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Fostering Computational Thinking in CS1 through Multilingual Game Development	Lee, Dongeun and El Ariss, Omar and Hu, Kaoning and Kwon, Kibum and Tapia, Jonathan	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Game-Based and Gamified Robotics Education: A Comparative Systematic Review and Design Guidelines	Mubarrat, Syed Tanzim and Min, Byung-Cheol and Shao, Tianyu and Smith, E. Cho and Benes, Bedrich and Magana, Alejandra and Mousas, Christos and Kao, Dominic	2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Serious game development as a creative learning experience: lessons learnt	Garneli, Varvara and Giannakos, Michail N. and Chorianopoulos, Konstantinos and Jaccheri, Letizia	2015	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
How Do Different Cognitive Styles Affect Learning Programming? Insights from a Game-Based Approach in Greek Schools	Theodoropoulos, Anastasios and Antoniou, Angeliki and Lepouras, George	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
GAMUT: GAME-based learning approach for teaching Unit Testing	Gomes, Renata Faria and Lelli, Val{e}ria	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Towards a new massive multiplayer online role playing game for introductory programming	Malliarakis, Christos and Satratzemi, Maya and Xinogalos, Stelios	2013	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
A Digital Game-based Learning Approach to Improve Students' Learning Performance of Senior High School Programming Courses	Xu, Xiang and Liu, Rui and Chen, Qinqin and Yang, Hairu	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Pyrates: Design and Evaluation of a Serious Game Aimed at Introducing Python Programming and Easing the Transition from Blocks	Branth{o}me, Matthieu	2024	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
You Hacked My Program! Teaching Cybersecurity using Game-based Learning	Tareque, Md. Hasan and Deutekom, Steven and Anvik, John and Bashir, Maimoona	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Parallel X: Redesigning of a Parallel Programming Educational Game with Semantic Foundations and Transfer Learning	McKee, Devon and Lin, Zhiyu and Fox, Boyd and Li, Jiahong and Zhu, Jichen and Seif El-Nasr, Magy and Sorensen, Tyler	2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Failure rates in introductory programming revisited	Watson, Christopher and Li, Frederick W.B.	2014	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Ne-course for learning programming	Figueiredo, Jos{e} and Gomes, Nat{a}lia and Garc{a} Pe{~n}alvo, Francisco Jos{e}	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Addressing Misconceptions in Introductory Programming: Automated Feedback in Integrated Development Environments	Fischer, Bj{o}rn and Birk, Fabian and Iwer, Eva-Maria and Panitz, Sven Eric and D{o}rner, Ralf	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Boosting Student Motivation through Game-based Learning in Programming Education with Gamify-IT	Mei{ss}ner, Niklas and Speth, Sandro and Krieger, Niklas and Becker, Steffen	2026	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
A Framework for Motivating Sketching Practice with Sketch-based Gameplay	Williford, Blake and Runyon, Matthew and Cherian, Josh and Li, Wayne and Linsey, Julie and Hammond, Tracy	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

ICEMT '24: Proceedings of the 2024 8th International Conference on Education and Multimedia Technology		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SA '17: SIGGRAPH Asia 2017 Symposium on Education		2017	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHI PLAY '22: Extended Abstracts of the 2022 Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICETC '24: Proceedings of the 2024 16th International Conference on Education Technology and Computers		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
FDG '25: Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on the Foundations of Digital Games		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IUI '24 Companion: Companion Proceedings of the 29th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Asian CHI '23: Proceedings of the Asian HCI Symposium 2023		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICSLT '24: Proceedings of the 2024 10th International Conference on e-Society, e-Learning and e-Technologies (ICSLT)		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
AICCC '24: Proceedings of the 2024 7th Artificial Intelligence and Cloud Computing Conference		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ITiCSE '15: Proceedings of the 2015 ACM Conference on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education		2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
WiPSCE '23: Proceedings of the 18th WiPSCE Conference on Primary and Secondary Computing Education Research		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
RESPECT 2025: Proceedings of the 2025 Conference on Research on Equitable and Sustained Participation in Engineering, Computing, and Technology		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IMX '24: Proceedings of the 2024 ACM International Conference on Interactive Media Experiences		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICIEI '24: Proceedings of the 2024 9th International Conference on Information and Education Innovations		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICDTE '22: Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Digital Technology in Education		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICETC '22: Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Education Technology and Computers		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
WiPSCE '24: Proceedings of the 19th WiPSCE Conference on Primary and Secondary Computing Education Research		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICIEAI '24: Proceedings of the 2024 2nd International Conference on Information Education and Artificial Intelligence		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SIGITE '23: Proceedings of the 24th Annual Conference on Information Technology Education		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHI PLAY Companion '24: Companion Proceedings of the 2024 Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
L@S '25: Proceedings of the Twelfth ACM Conference on Learning @ Scale		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

IUI '23 Companion: Companion Proceedings of the 28th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CompSysTech '24: Proceedings of the International Conference on Computer Systems and Technologies 2024		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
L@S '24: Proceedings of the Eleventh ACM Conference on Learning @ Scale		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ETRA '24: Proceedings of the 2024 Symposium on Eye Tracking Research and Applications		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
UMAP '25: Proceedings of the 33rd ACM Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICETC '23: Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Education Technology and Computers		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SIGCITE '25: Proceedings of the 26th ACM Annual Conference on Cybersecurity & Information Technology Education		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SIGCSE 2024: Proceedings of the 55th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education V. 1		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICEEL '24: Proceeding of the 2024 8th International Conference on Education and E-Learning		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SIGCSE 2024: Proceedings of the 55th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education V. 2		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
WCCCE '24: Proceedings of the 26th Western Canadian Conference on Computing Education		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SIGSETS 2025: Proceedings of the 56th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education V. 1		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
PETRA '24: Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on PErvasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
AfriCHI '25: Proceedings of the 5th Biennial African Human Computer Interaction Conference		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IUI '26: Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces		2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
NISS '24: Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Networking, Intelligent Systems and Security		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICEDS '24: Proceedings of the 2024 5th International Conference on Education Development and Studies		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICER '24: Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research - Volume 1		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ITiCSE 2024: Proceedings of the 2024 on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education V. 2		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
HCAIep '23: Proceedings of the 2023 Conference on Human Centered Artificial Intelligence: Education and Practice		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SIGSETS 2025: Proceedings of the 56th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education V. 2		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

MUM '23: Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Multimedia		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Mindtrek '23: Proceedings of the 26th International Academic Mindtrek Conference		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHIGREECE '23: Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference of the ACM Greek SIGCHI Chapter		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SBQS '23: Proceedings of the XXII Brazilian Symposium on Software Quality		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
NordiCHI '24: Proceedings of the 13th Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICSE-SEET '24: Proceedings of the 46th International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering Education and Training		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ITiCSE 2025: Proceedings of the 30th ACM Conference on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education V. 1		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SIGUCCS '26: Proceedings of the 2026 ACM SIGUCCS Annual Conference		2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SIGCSE Virtual 2024: Proceedings of the 2024 on ACM Virtual Global Computing Education Conference V. 2		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SIGCSE Virtual 2024: Proceedings of the 2024 on ACM Virtual Global Computing Education Conference V. 1		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
NordiCHI '22 Adjunct: Adjunct Proceedings of the 2022 Nordic Human-Computer Interaction Conference		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHI EA '21: Extended Abstracts of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems		2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IDC '25: Proceedings of the 24th Interaction Design and Children		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CompEd 2023: Proceedings of the ACM Conference on Global Computing Education Vol 2		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ACE '25: Proceedings of the 27th Australasian Computing Education Conference		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ITiCSE 2025: Proceedings of the 30th ACM Conference on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education V. 2		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
WSC '23: Proceedings of the Winter Simulation Conference		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ASSETS '24: Proceedings of the 26th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IECT '25: Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Intelligent Education and Computer Technology		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IC3-2024: Proceedings of the 2024 Sixteenth International Conference on Contemporary Computing		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICAIES '25: Proceedings of the 2025 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Educational Systems		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

CHIItaly '25: Proceedings of the 16th Biannual Conference of the Italian SIGCHI Chapter		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
KUI '24: Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Culture and Computer Science: from Humanism to Digital Humanities		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
HCAIep '24: Proceedings of the 2024 Conference on Human Centred Artificial Intelligence - Education and Practice		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICIEI '23: Proceedings of the 2023 8th International Conference on Information and Education Innovations		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Academic Mindtrek '22: Proceedings of the 25th International Academic Mindtrek Conference		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHIItaly '23: Proceedings of the 15th Biannual Conference of the Italian SIGCHI Chapter		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICEMT '25: Proceedings of the 2025 9th International Conference on Education and Multimedia Technology		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Gaming for middle school students: building virtual worlds	Hardnett, Charles R.	2008	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ASSETS '25: Proceedings of the 27th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IUI '26 Companion: Companion Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces		2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
AI Literacy in K-12 and Higher Education in the Wake of Generative AI: An Integrative Review	Gu, Xingjian (Lance) and Ericson, Barbara J.	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Deploying team-based learning at undergraduate software engineering courses	Matalonga, Santiago and Mousqu\{e}s, Gast\{o}n and Bia, Alejandro	2017	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Code hunt: experience with coding contests at scale	Bishop, Judith and Horspool, R. Nigel and Xie, Tao and Tillmann, Nikolai and de Halleux, Jonathan	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Exploring Similarities and Differences in a set of Linked Multiple-site Design Sessions with Children	Read, Janet and Sim, Gavin and Fails, Jerry Alan and Boden, Marie A and Korte, Jessica L and Bhatnagar, Sanjana and Hope Borchardt, Lilly and Constantin, Aurora and Gavrilesco, Dina and Wilson, Cara and Good, Judith and Andries, Valentina and Eriksson, Eva	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CISing Up Service Learning: A Systematic Review of Service Learning Experiences in Computer and Information Science	Robledo Yamamoto, Fujiko and Barker, Lecia and Voida, Amy	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Interactive educational simulations for promoting the comprehension of basic compiler construction concepts	Rodriguez-Cerezo, Daniel and G\{o}mez-Albarr\{a}n, Mercedes and Sierra-Rodr\{i}guez, Jos\{e}-Luis	2013	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Educational software engineering: where software engineering, education, and gaming meet	Xie, Tao and Tillmann, Nikolai and de Halleux, Jonathan	2013	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Culturally Situated Computational Thinking: Interactive Physical Computing in Cultural K-12 Contexts	Ru, Ze and Ibrahim, Malak and Chyngyz, Alikhan and Jawad, Adan and Melniczuk, Amy	2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Facilitating human interaction in an online programming course	Warren, Joe and Rixner, Scott and Greiner, John and Wong, Stephen	2014	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Comprehension First: Evaluating a Novel Pedagogy and Tutoring System for Program Tracing in CS1	Nelson, Greg L. and Xie, Benjamin and Ko, Amy J.	2017	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Project-based app programming: tools and techniques for a successful novice-focused app development course	Makutonin, Michael and Chen, Samuel	2020	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Alternate reality games for computer science education	Hakulinen, Lasse	2013	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Reflections on Training Next-Gen Industry Workforce on Secure Software Development	Espinha Gasiba, Tiago and Iosif, Andrei-Cristian and Suppan, Santiago and Lechner, Ulrike and Pinto-Albuquerque, Maria	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Addressing the Prior Knowledge Challenge in Level-Based Educational Games: An Artificial Neural Network-Inspired Framework	Zhao, Yuqian	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Hour of Code: Classroom Escape	Žufić, J. and Žufić, A. and Bodiš, S.	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Educational Game-Theme Based Instructional Module for Teaching Introductory Programming	Rajeev, Sarika and Sharma, Sharad	2018	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Design and First Insights of a Case Study on Storified Programming MOOCs	Hagedorn, Christiane and Staubitz, Thomas and Teusner, Ralf and Meinel, Christoph	2019	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Developing And Executing Pedagogical Virtual Game-Based Learning for Java Programming	Azmi, Tengku Muhammad Hanafi Tengku and Baharudin, Suzana and Ahmad, Suzana and Diah, Norizan Mat	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Methodology for developing gamification-based learning programming language framework	Khaleel, Firas Layth and Ashaari, Noraidah Sahari and Wook, Tengku Siti Meriam Tengku and Ismail, Amirah	2017	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Enhancing Sequence Coding Skills in Lower Primary School through Affordable Game-based Learning: A Case Study in Thailand	Vathanakulkachorn, Vichamaporn and Pichitpreecha, Sarun and Supakwong, Supawat	2023	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
An authoring toolkit design for educational game content	Abdullah, Nor Aniza and Raja, Raja Hafiz and Kamaruddin, Ahmad and Razak, Zaidi and Yusoff, Mohd. Yakub Zulkifli Bin Mohd.	2008	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
An experimental evaluation of scaffolded educational games design for programming	Jantan, Siti Robaya and Aljunid, Syed Ahmad	2012	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted

A Propriety Multiplatform Game-Based Learning Game to Learn Object-Oriented Programming	Wong, Yoke Seng and Yatim, Maizatul Hayati Mohamad	2018	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Optimizing Player Engagement in an Educational Virtual Game through Fuzzy Logic-based Challenge Adaptation	Krouska, Akrivi and Troussas, Christos and Voutos, Yorghos and Mylonas, Phivos and Sgouropoulou, Cleo	2023	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Revolutionizing C++ Programming Education: A Gamified Interactive Educational Game	Nguyen, Dung	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Enhancing Confidence in Using Computational Thinking Skills via Playing a Serious Game: A Case Study to Increase Motivation in Learning Computer Programming	Kazimoglu, Cagin	2020	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Evaluating Learner's Usability Using Codenite Educational Battle Royal Programming Language Game	Nobnop, Ratchanon and Tongpaeng, Yootthapong and Thammapalo, Narongrit and Rittidech, Chayangkun and Wira, Marcel and Thawonmas, Ruck	2023	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
GidgetML: An Adaptive Serious Game for Enhancing First Year Programming Labs	Miljanovic, Michael A. and Bradbury, Jeremy S.	2020	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Exploring Game Elements in Learning Programming: An Empirical Evaluation	Santos, Adriano Lages dos and Souza, Maurício R. de A. and Dayrell, Marcella and Figueiredo, Eduardo	2018	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Serious games for learning programming languages	Mitamura, Tamotsu and Suzuki, Yasuhiro and Oohori, Takahumi	2012	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
A Review of Gamification for Learning Programming Fundamental	Shahid, Mahwish and Wajid, Afifa and Haq, Kamran Ul and Saleem, Imran and Shujja, Abdul Haseeb	2019	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Comparison of game engines for serious games	Pavkov, Sanja and Franković, Ivona and Hoić-Božić, Nataša	2017	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Using an Online Serious Game to Teach Basic Programming Concepts and Facilitate Gameful Experiences for High School Students	Montes, Hernán and Hijón-Neira, Raquel and Pérez-Marín, Diana and Montes, Sergio	2021	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Discovering Programming Talent and Improving Learning Motivation with CodeCombat in K-12 Education	Choi, Wan Chong and Choi, Iek Chong	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Investigating the role of purposeful goals on novices' engagement in a programming game	Lee, Michael J. and Ko, Amy J.	2012	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted

ARCode: Augmented Reality Application for Learning Elementary Computer Programming	Sittiyuno, Sirawit and Chaipah, Kornchawal	2019	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Comparison of Students' Motivation for Programming Computer Game and Educational Robot Using the Game of Marbles	Kunovic, I. and Krzic, A. Sovic	2021	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Enchanting e-learning through the use of interactive-feedback loop in digital games	Kazimoglu, Cagin and Kiernan, Mary and Bacon, Liz	2010	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Learning by game creation in introductory programming course: 5-Year-long study	Paralič, M. and Pietriková, E.	2014	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Research through Design of Meta-Integrated Programming Educational Games: Uncovering Mechanisms via LDA Topic Modeling	Guo, Shuai and Liu, Da-Wei and Zhai, Chang	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Developing an educational programming game for children with ADHD	Galeos, Christos and Karpouzis, Kostas and Tsatiris, George	2020	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Using educational games in learning introductory programming: A pilot study on students' perceptions	Ibrahim, Roslina and Semarak, Jalan and Lumpur, Kuala and Jaafar, Azizah	2010	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Teste de Usabilidade: Perspectivas Futuras da Experiência de Meninas em um Jogo de Lógica de Programação	Kenia Reis and Ângelo Feitosa and José Santos Junior and Matheus Araújo and Simone Aquino and Varley Sa	2025	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Accepted
Hello Food: um jogo para praticar conceitos de algoritmos para iniciantes na computação	Jeniffer Macena and Fernanda Pires and Marcela Pessoa and Rafaela Melo	2022	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Accepted
Uso da Taxonomia de Bloom Revisada em um Jogo de RPG Educacional sobre Conceitos Introdutórios de Programação	Rayssa Santana and Claudia Rizzi and Clodis Boscaroli	2025	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Accepted
RobotCode: um jogo educacional para auxiliar na aprendizagem de lógica de programação	Fabrizio Honda and Rafaela Melo and Fernanda Pires and Marcela Pessoa	2023	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Accepted
Um jogo para o ensino de programação em Python baseado na taxonomia de Bloom	Pasqueline Scaico and Diego Marques and Leandro Melo and Max Azevedo and Sinval Neto and Anderson Oliveira and Josinaldo Alves Júnior and Marcelo Labanca and Alexandre Scaico	2012	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Accepted
CODE_DUNGEON: um serious game para auxiliar no aprendizado de programação	Gabriel Oliveira and Elisa Boff	2023	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Accepted

Robô Sniper como ferramenta de ensino para as aulas de física no tiro parabólico	Claudenir Alves Filho and Gustavo Dutra and Ricardo Schirmer and Anselmo Cukla and Fernanda Mota and Solon Bevilacqua	2024	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Rejected
Localization and its impact on achieving SDGs and transitioning to post-SDGs in Indonesia	Andi Besse Rimba and Ichiro Sato and Kei Endo	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
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A cognitive-experiential approach to modelling web navigation	Paul {van Schaik} and Jonathan Ling	2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
Reprint of: Effects of experiential service learning in improving community engagement perception, sustainability awareness, and data analytics competency	W. Eric Lee and Arif Perdana	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
An annotated bibliography of technology-based training	M Labinger and P J Finch	1986	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Chapter 13 - Interactive Media and the Writer	Timothy Garrand	2010	Science@Direct	Rejected
Experiences of immersive virtual reality in healthcare clinical training for nursing and allied health students: A mixed studies systematic review	Tze Ching Shyanne Quah and Ying Lau and Wen Wei Ang and Siew Tiang Lau	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 3 - The scenarios	Arthur Winzenried and Derek Law and Phillip Hughes and Doug Johnson and Sue Healey and David Warner and Katie Hannan and Giuseppe Giovenco	2010	Science@Direct	Rejected
Learning processes, learner attributes and simulations	Peter Goodyear and Melanie Njoo and Hans Hijne and Jos {J.A. van Berkum}	1991	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Applying the technology acceptance model in a study of the factors affecting usage of the Taiwan digital archives system	Jon-Chao Hong and Ming-Yueh Hwang and Hsuan-Fang Hsu and Wan-Tzu Wong and Mei-Yung Chen	2011	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Systematic reviews of the effectiveness of developmental prevention programs in reducing delinquency, aggression, and bullying	David P. Farrington and Hannah Gaffney and Friedrich Lösel and Maria M. Ttofi	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Multi-agent systems support for Community-Based Learning	Yugyung Lee and Quddus Chong	2003	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Investigating Students' Intention to Use M-Learning:	Mohammed Abdullatif Almulla	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Exploring the process of learning in human ecology	Jonathan Sajiwandani	1993	Science@Direct	Rejected
Utilizing Gamification, Artificial Intelligence, and mHealth for the Professional Development of Maternal Care Providers: Exploratory Pilot Cross-Sectional Study Assessing Providers' Satisfaction in Primary Health Care Centers in Lebanon	Mohamad Alameddine and Nadine Sabra and Nour {El Arnaout} and Asmaa {El Dakdouki} and Mahmoud {El Jaouni} and Randa Hamadeh and Abed Shanaa and Shadi Saleh	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Points and the Delivery of Gameful Experiences in a Gamified Environment: Framework Development and Case Analysis	Sungjin Park and Sangkyun Kim	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Community influences on learning: Reference notes	Herbert J. Walberg and Geneva D. Haertel	1984	Science@Direct	Rejected

Model-driven processes and tools to design robot-based generative learning objects for computer science education	Vytautas Štuikys and Renata Burbaitė and Kristina Bespalova and Giedrius Ziberkas	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
111th Annual Meeting of the American Association of Colleges of Pharmacy, Seattle, Washington, July 10–14, 2010		2010	Science@Direct	Rejected
113th Annual Meeting of the American Association of Colleges of Pharmacy, Kissimmee, FL, July 14-18, 2012		2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
Use of ICT Teaching-Learning Methods make School Math Blossom	Aija Cunska and Inga Savicka	2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
Adopting extended reality? A systematic review of manufacturing training and teaching applications	Andrea {de Giorgio} and Fabio Marco Monetti and Antonio Maffei and Mario Romero and Lihui Wang	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Use and Design of Virtual Reality–Supported Learning Scenarios in the Vocational Qualification of Nursing Professionals: Scoping Review	Jenny-Victoria Steindorff and Lisa-Marie Redlich and Denny Paulicke and Patrick Jahn	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Elucidating usage of e-government learning: A perspective of the extended technology acceptance model	Stacy Huey-Pyng Shyu and Jen-Hung Huang	2011	Science@Direct	Rejected
Contextualised MALL: L2 Chinese students in target and non-target country	Orit Ezra and Anat Cohen	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
RETRACTED: Building an online educational platform to promote creative and affective thinking in special education	Chunfei Tu and Yermek Nurymov and Zaure Umirzakova and Anna Berestova	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Developing Innovative Ideas Through High Intellectual and Creative Educational Multimedia Technologies	Larisa V. Shavinina and Evgueni A. Ponomarev	2003	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Improving Pediatric Asthma Care Through Asthma Apps: A Narrative Review	Lauren Hillam Wittwer and Elizabeth Walters and Katherine Jordan	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
An interplay among digital transformation, AI adoption and inclusive education	Anand Thakur and Kavita Singla and Kamini Singla and Km Ankita Mishra and Parwinder Kaur and Simran Kaur	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Digital learning in schools: What does it take beyond digital technology?	Michael Sailer and Julia Murböck and Frank Fischer	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
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European Resuscitation Council Guidelines 2021: Education for resuscitation	Robert Greif and Andrew Lockey and Jan Breckwoldt and Francesc Carmona and Patricia Conaghan and Artem Kuzovlev and Lucas Pflanzl-Knizacek and Ferenc Sari and Salma Shammet and Andrea Scapigliati and Nigel Turner and Joyce Yeung and Koenraad G. Monsieurs	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
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The potential of digital tools to enhance mathematics and science learning in secondary schools: A context-specific meta-analysis	Delia Hillmayr and Lisa Ziernwald and Frank Reinhold and Sarah I. Hofer and Kristina M. Reiss	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Learning with a strategic management simulation game: A case study	Mark Loon and Jason Evans and Clive Kerridge	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Tracking e-learning through published papers: A systematic review	Helena Rodrigues and Filomena Almeida and Vanessa Figueiredo and Sara L. Lopes	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Chapter 21 - Aesthetic Computing*	Paul A. Fishwick	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
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Informal learning recognition through a cloud ecosystem	Francisco José García-Peñalvo and Mark Johnson and Gustavo Ribeiro Alves and Miroslav Minović and Miguel Ángel Conde-González	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
GidgetML: an adaptive serious game for enhancing first year programming labs	Miljanovic, Michael A. and Bradbury, Jeremy S.	2020	ACM Digital Library	Duplicated
How to prepare for conversations with children about suspicions of sexual abuse? Evaluation of an interactive virtual reality training for student teachers	Niels Krause and Elsa Gewehr and Hermann Barbe and Marie Merschhemke and Frieda Mensing and Bruno Siegel and Jürgen L. Müller and Renate Volbert and Peter Fromberger and Anett Tamm and Simone Pülschen	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected

Effects of E-Learning in a Continuing Education Context on Nursing Care: Systematic Review of Systematic Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed-Studies Reviews	Geneviève Rouleau and Marie-Pierre Gagnon and José Côté and Julie Payne-Gagnon and Emilie Hudson and Carl-Ardy Dubois and Julien Bouix-Picasso	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Offline Digital Education for Postregistration Health Professions: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis by the Digital Health Education Collaboration	Pawel Posadzki and Malgorzata M Bala and Bhone Myint Kyaw and Monika Semwal and Ushashree Divakar and Magdalena Koperny and Agnieszka Sliwka and Josip Car	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Developing a Scratch-based coding achievement test	Ömer Demir and Süleyman Sadi Seferoğlu	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Systematic mapping of computational thinking in preschool children	Everton Carlos Martins and Letícia Gabrielly Zacano {da Silva} and Vânia Paula de Almeida Neris	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Leveling up: Are non-gamers and women disadvantaged in a virtual world classroom?	Clyde A. Warden and James O. Stanworth and Chi-Cheng Chang	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
A conceptual model of students' reflective practice for the development of employability competences, supported by an online learning platform	Perry Heymann and Ellen Bastiaens and Anne Jansen and Peter {van Rosmalen} and Simon Beusaert	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Youth as energy citizens or passive actors? A critical review of energy transition scholarship	Arwa Jaradat and Bram Noble and Greg Poelzer	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Challenges, opportunities, and prospects of adopting and using smart digital technologies in learning environments: An iterative review	Siyabonga Mhlongo and Khanyisile Mbatha and Boitumelo Ramatsetse and Reuben Dlamini	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Decade of Research on the Use of Three-Dimensional Virtual Worlds in Health Care: A Systematic Literature Review	Reza Ghanbarzadeh and Amir Hossein Ghapanchi and Michael Blumenstein and Amir Talaei-Khoei	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
Understanding the challenges and requirements for facilitating iStar learning: An empirical study with iStar learners	Tong Li and Qixiang Zhou and Yunduo Wang and Haonan Xiong and Wenxing Liu and Ning Ge	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Digital Education for Health Professions on Smoking Cessation Management: Systematic Review by the Digital Health Education Collaboration	Monika Semwal and Penny Whiting and Ram Bajpai and Shweta Bajpai and Bhone Myint Kyaw and Lorainne {Tudor Car}	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Learning by doing: Chem-E-Car® motivating experience	C. Negro and N. Merayo and M.C. Monte and A. Balea and E. Fuente and A. Blanco	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Gamification at the workplace: a theoretical perspective on training and development	Aaradhana Rukadikar and Komal Khandelwal	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
A concise review of intelligent game agent	Hui Li and Xinyi Pang and Bixia Sun and Kexin Liu	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected

Fueling entrepreneurship in STEM: Unveiling trends, educational programs, and their impact	M. Eval Setiawan and Hadi Suwono and Hadi Nur and Sulisetijono Sulisetijono and Husamah Husamah	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Library instruction and information literacy 2019	Tessa Withorn and Joanna {Messer Kimmitt} and Carolyn Caffrey and Anthony Andora and Cristina Springfield and Dana Ospina and Maggie Clarke and George Martinez and Amalia Castañeda and Aric Haas and Wendolyn Vermeer	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Adapting CTF challenges into virtual cybersecurity learning environments	Stylianios Karagiannis and Emmanouil Magkos	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Promoting perceived creativity and innovative behavior: Benefits of future problem-solving programs for higher education students	Dorit Alt and Yoav Kapshuk and Heli Dekel	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
The impact of entrepreneurial education on key entrepreneurial competencies: A systematic review of learning strategies and tools	Erika Branca and Johanna Vanderstraeten and Hendrik Slabbinck and Isabo Maria R. Maes	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Current practices for assessing clinical judgment in nursing students and new graduates: A scoping review	Michelle E. Bussard and Mary Ann Jessee and Majeda M. El-Banna and Mary Ann Cantrell and Intima Alrimawi and Nadine M. Marchi and Lisa I. Gonzalez and Keith Rischer and Michelle L. Coy and Mari Poledna and Patrick Lavoie	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Editorial — Special Issue on Computational Thinking and Coding in Childhood	Kate Howland and Judith Good and Judy Robertson and Andrew Manches	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Levels of Community Change: A Game to Teach About Policy, System, and Environment Change	Carol A. Smathers and Theresa M. Ferrari	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Community education on the health impacts of bushfires: Evaluation of an online pilot short course in Tasmania, Australia	Sharon L. Campbell and James J.R. Brady and Carina C. Anderson and Myriam Ziou and Duncan Sinclair and Fay H. Johnston and Penelope J. Jones	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
A systematic review of mindset interventions in mathematics classrooms: What works and what does not?	Phuong Bui and Nonmanut Pongsakdi and Jake McMullen and Erno Lehtinen and Minna M. Hannula-Sormunen	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Augmented reality and robotics in education: A systematic literature review	Christina Pasalidou and Chris Lytridis and Avgoustos Tsinakos and Nikolaos Fachantidis	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Understand, develop and enhance the learning process with big data	Soraya Sedkaoui and Mounia Khelfaoui	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected

Effects of games centered professional learning on physical education outcomes in primary school: RCT of the Professional Learning for Understanding Games Education (PLUNGE) intervention	A. Miller and E. Christensen and J. Sproule and L. Annis-Brown and N. Eather and D. Lubans	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Qualitative Analysis of Youth Feedback of Nutrition School Enrichment Kits	Adam Losey and Wanda Koszewski and Donnia Behrends and Marilyn Schnepf and Georgia Jones	2011	Science@Direct	Rejected
Knowledge Network for the Development of Software Projects (KnowNetSoft)	Justyna Patalas-Maliszewska and Sławomir Kłós	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Ten Years of En Route Critical Care Training	Mathieu Boutonnet and Pierre Pasquier and Laurent Raynaud and Laurent Vitiello and Jérôme Bancarel and Sébastien Coste and Guillaume Pelée {de Saint Maurice} and Sylvain Ausset	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Integrating a digital pedagogy approach into online teaching: are academic librarians at Universities of Technology in South Africa prepared?	Mousin Omarsaib	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Teachers' practices in the use of digital technology to promote students' self-regulated learning and metacognition: A systematic review	Désirée Delia Diana Fahrni and Glenna Iten and Doreen Prasse and Tina Hascher	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Conceptualising learning from resilient performance: A scoping literature review	Helene Degerman and Andreas Wallo	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Effects of digital badges on pupils' computational thinking and learning motivation in computer science	Yuhan Dong and Hongliang Ma and Hongying Li and Bin Jing and Hongchao Liu	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Let's play and learn: Educational escape room to improve mental health knowledge in undergraduate nursing students	Marta Arrue and Nerea Suárez and Maider Ugartemendia-Yerobi and Izaro Babarro	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Programming in early childhood education: A systematic review	Elena Macrides and Ourania Miliou and Charoula Angeli	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Utilization, challenges, and training needs of digital health technologies: Perspectives from healthcare professionals	Ruby Khan and Sumbal Khan and Hailah M. Almohaimeed and Amany I. Almars and Bakht Pari	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
The Celsius Game: An experiential activity on management education simulating the complex challenges for the two-degree climate change target	Fernanda Carreira and Ana Carolina Aguiar and Fabiano Onça and Mario Monzoni	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Immersive insights: A qualitative systematic review and thematic synthesis of views, experiences, health and wellbeing of students and educators using virtual reality in nursing and midwifery education	Sylvester Odame-Amoabeng and Ayse Akalin and Florence D'haenens and Sandra Tricas-Sauras and Yan-Shing Chang	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Gamification and neurological motor rehabilitation in children and adolescents: a systematic review	M. Pimentel-Ponce and R.P. Romero-Galisteo and R. Palomo-Carrión and E. Pinero-Pinto and J. {Antonio Merchán-Baeza} and M. Ruiz-Muñoz and J. Oliver-Pece and M. González-Sánchez	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected

A Scoping Review of Teaching and Assessment Strategies for Pharmaceutical Calculations in Health Professions Education	Mary E. Fredrickson and Anna Nogid and Sharon Wu and Apryl N. Peddi and Rachel Whitney and Melissa Gratz and Jennifer N. Wisniewski	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Diverse Categories of Programming Learning Activities could be Performed within Scratch	Maria Kordaki	2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
Conceptualizing AI literacies for children and youth: A systematic review on the design of AI literacy educational programs	Osnat Atias and Areej Mawasi	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
O31 Determining Low-Income Fathers' Preferred mHealth Nutrition-Related Topics, Features, and Delivery Methods	Amy Mobley and Kim Gans and Kari Adamsons and Elder Varela and Jamie Zeldman	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
A systematic review of integrating computational thinking in early childhood education	Jiahong Su and Weipeng Yang	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Developing authentic leadership as a starting point to responsible management: A Canadian university case study	Anne-Marie Corriveau	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 7 - 3D visualization for anatomy education	Bernhard Preim and Renata Raidou and Noeska Smit and Kai Lawonn	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
A multi-perspective study on Artificial Intelligence in Education: grants, conferences, journals, software tools, institutions, and researchers	Xieling Chen and Haoran Xie and Gwo-Jen Hwang	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
A micro-credential approach for life-long learning in the urban renewable energy sector	Mattia {De Rosa} and Olga Glumac and Vincenzo Bianco and Fabiano Pallonetto	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Dual-contrast pedagogy for AI literacy in upper elementary schools	Yun Dai	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
225. Baby Town: A Role-Playing Board Game and Curriculum to Highlight the Challenges of Teenage Parenthood in a Destigmatizing Manner	Ellen McCammon and Amy Moore and Crystal P. Tyler and Mason Arrington and Patrick Jagoda and Ashlyn Sparrow and Melissa Gilliam	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Nursing students' perception of digital technology in clinical education among undergraduate programs: A qualitative systematic review	Huijuan Ma and Aifang Niu and Jing Tan and Jing Wang and Yu Luo	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Music Background in the Classroom: Its Role in the Development of Social-emotional Competence in Preschool Children	Dana Jucan and Anca Simion	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Computational thinking training with technology for non-information undergraduates	Hsing-Yu Hou and Somya Agrawal and Chin-Feng Lee	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Changing professional demands in sustainable regional development: a curriculum design process to meet transboundary competence	Angelique Lansu and Jo Boon and Peter B. Sloep and Rietje {van Dam-Mieras}	2013	Science@Direct	Rejected
226. Hearsay: A Storytelling Card Game to Increase Knowledge and Awareness of Contraception and Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (Prep) Among High School Students	Ellen McCammon and Amy Moore and Crystal P. Tyler and Mason Arrington and Patrick Jagoda and Ashlyn Sparrow and Melissa Gilliam	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Exploring four decades of research in Computers & Education	Olaf Zawacki-Richter and Colin Latchem	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected

Eutopia-Mt. teaching mediation skills using multiplayer on-line role playing games	Orazio Miglino and Alberto Venditti and Alessandra Delli Veneri and Andrea {Di Ferdinando}	2010	Science@Direct	Rejected
Development and Evaluation of Two 3D-Simulated Practice Learning Environments	Stephen Farrier and Thomas M. Connolly and Nikolina Tsvetkova and Mario Soflano and Petros Papadopoulos	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
How simulation teaching is revolutionizing our relationship with cardiology	Théo Pezel and Augustin Coisne and Fabien Picard and Pascal Gueret	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Beyond the fog of war: Mining social dynamics and genre shaping in the StarCraft universe	Erkut Altındağ and Yavuz Selim Balcioglu	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Exploring facilitation in virtual simulation in nursing education: A scoping review	Lena Günterberg Heyn and Espen Andreas Brembo and Kirsten Røland Byermoen and Caroline Cruaud and Hilde Eide and Jill Flo and Anita Nordsteien and Grith Overgaard and Hugrun Ösp Egilsdottir	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Efficacy of active teaching methods for distance learning in undergraduate nursing education: a systematic review	Stefano Mancin and Marco Sguanci and Veronica Pipitone and Angelica Testori and Maria Grazia {De Marinis} and Michela Piredda	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effect of the virtual PC-simulation MicroSim on performance of simulated emergency scenarios	O. Meyer and A. Felber and C. Hennig and C. Gallschuetz	2010	Science@Direct	Rejected
Education for sustainable development through e-learning in higher education: experiences from Portugal	Ulisses Miranda Azeiteiro and Paula Bacelar-Nicolau and Fernando J.P. Caetano and Sandra Caeiro	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
The trajectory of artificial intelligence for competency-based personalised learning: past, present and future	Omkar Dastane and Jason Turner and Alan Nankervis	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Engaging consumers in circular lifestyles: Analysing innovation patterns through a virtual exhibition designed to counter the throw-away society	Mariann Szabó and Jan Gimkiewicz and Ahmad Alaraj	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Suicide prevention in Hong Kong: pushing boundaries while building bridges	Paul Siu Fai Yip and Eric D. Caine and Cheuk Yui Yeung and Yik Wa Law and Rainbow Tin Hung Ho	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Best practices for teaching pharmacology to undergraduate nursing students: A systematic review of the literature	Manu Gill and Elizabeth Andersen and Norma Hilsmann	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Factors influencing postgraduate nursing students' engagement with online learning in higher education: A mixed methods literature review	Anthony Chambers and Clare Whitfield	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Analysis of effective factors in the acceptance rate of E-learning at the time of Covid-19 outbreak	Hodjat Hamidi and Leila Amirfazli	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Exploring factors influencing the acceptance of visual programming environment among boys and girls in primary schools	Gary Cheng	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected

Interventions to promote resilience in children and adolescents: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials	Zhengyang Mei and Chenyi Cai and Tingfeng Wang and Yang Yang and Chifong Lam and Yuanzhuo Zhang and Wen Zhao and Yu Shi and Shulai Luo and Shi Luo	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Gamification and accessibility	Keyonda Smith and Sandra Schamroth Abrams	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Virtual Interface With Kinect 3D Sensor for Interaction With Bedridden People:	Vitor Hugo Carvalho and José Eusébio	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Intergenerational interventions and their impact on active aging: A systematic review	Michele Savino and Lisa {De Luca} and Annalaura Nocentini and Ersilia Menesini	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Exploring the hierarchical structure of human plans via program generation	Carlos G. Correa and Sophia Sanborn and Mark K. Ho and Frederick Callaway and Nathaniel D. Daw and Thomas L. Griffiths	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Participatory culture meets critical practice	Cassandra Scharber and Kris Isaacson and Tracey Pyscher and Cynthia Lewis	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 18 - Advances in the educational strategies in personalized learning for children with autism spectrum disorders	Kanwaljit Kaur and Jasvinder Singh Bhatti	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Special Issue: Multidisciplinary M&S	Agostino G. Bruzzone	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
Exploring how individual traits influence enjoyment in a mobile learning game	Youngkyun Baek and Achraf Touati	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Keeping up with technology: Teaching parallel, distributed, and high-performance computing	Sushil Prasad and Sheikh Ghafoor and Martina Barnas and Felix Wolf and Erik Saule and Noemi Rodriguez and Rizos Sakellariou	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Design thinking in nursing education: A scoping review	Dongyu Wang and Yanan Deng and Lan Zeng and Lixia Dong and Ruben Martin Payo and Fengying Zhang	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
A meta-analysis of teaching and learning computer programming: Effective instructional approaches and conditions	Ronny Scherer and Fazilat Siddiq and Bárbara {Sánchez Viveros}	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Exploring practical nursing skills acquisition through gamified computerized learning: A phenomenological study	Chun-Chih Lin and Chin-Yen Han and Ya-Ling Huang and Han-Chang Ku and Li-Chin Chen	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Virtual-tutoring-supported teaching for Geometrical Product Specification	Anna Sorgatz and Juliane Schuldt and Sophie Gröger	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Unboxing autonomous motivation, controlled motivation, and oral skills among EFL learners: Insights into gamification through the lens of broaden-and-build theory	Jiao Song and Ru Wang and Xinyuan Wu and Zhiyu Zhang	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effectiveness of designing and evaluating i-STAR applications in pediatric nursing courses	Hui-Man Huang and Yu-Wen Fang	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected

Analysis on quality of learning in e-Learning platforms	Veeramanickam M. R. M. and P. Ramesh	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Constructivist, Modeling Methodology for the Design of Educational Card Games	Maria Kordaki	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
A synthetic review of learning theories, elements and virtual environment simulation types to improve learning within higher education	Manisha {Hari Rajan} and Cristan Herbert and Patsie Polly	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Teaching, learning and assessment of the affective domain of undergraduate students: A scoping review	Ms Lizelle Potgieter and Celia Filmalter and Carin Maree	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Health and safety induction training in the construction industry: a review	Ndaleni Phinias Rantsatsi	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Social energy games for smart and connected residential communities: Mechanism design	Huijeong Kim and Jaehyun Go and Hemanth Devarapalli and Ilias Billionis and Panagiota Karava and James E. Braun	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Real-life Evaluation of an Interactive Versus Noninteractive e-Learning Module on Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease for Medical Licentiate Students in Zambia: Web-Based, Mixed Methods Randomized Controlled Trial	Elena Schnieders and Freda Röhr and Misho Mbewe and Aubrey Shanzi and Astrid Berner-Rodoreda and Sandra Barteit and Valérie R Louis and Petros Andreadis and Gardner Syakantu and Florian Neuhann	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Can children's instructional gameplay activity be used as a predictive indicator of reading skills?	Jenny M. Thomson and Njål Foldnes and Per Henning Uppstad and Morten Njå and Oddny Judith Solheim and Kjersti Lundetræ	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Examining the potential impact of digital game making in curricula based teaching: Initial observations	Thomas Hughes-Roberts and David Brown and Helen Boulton and Andrew Burton and Nicholas Shopland and Dominic Martinovs	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Designing for Teen Mental Health: An exploration of the co-design of virtual reality in the public library setting	Elin A. Björling and Kung Jin Lee and Jin Ha Lee and Ruican Zhang and Sean Roth and Juan Rubio	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Evaluating digital mental health interventions for Middle East and North Africa children and adolescents affected by armed conflict: A systematic review	Rawan Iriqat and Teresita Rocha-Jimenez and Margarita {Romero de la Cruz}	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Examining learners' engagement patterns and knowledge outcome in an experiential learning intervention for youth's social media literacy	Wenting Zou and Amanda {Purington Drake} and Philipp K. Masur and Janis Whitlock and Natalie N. Bazarova	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Embedding cultural safety in nursing education: A scoping review of strategies and approaches	Rishma Chooniedass and Manuela Reekie and Jacqueline Denison and Adaleena Mercuri and Roula Nawara and Natasha Purcell and Megan Oelke and Robert Janke	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected

Learning practical nursing skills in simulation centers – A narrative review	Inger Helen Sekse Hilleren and Bjørg Christiansen and Ida Torunn Bjørk	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
EASIER: A new model for online learning of minimally invasive surgery skills	Ignacio Oropesa and Luisa F. Sánchez-Peralta and Carmen {Guzmán García} and Magdalena K. Chmarra and Krisztina Berner-Juhos and Calin Tiu and Christos Mettouris and George A. Papadopoulos and Andreas Papadopoulos and José {Blas Pagador} and Joeri Post and Jenny Dankelman and Ana González-Segura and Francisco M. Sánchez-Margallo and Enrique J. Gómez	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Impact of asynchronous online cancer education for nurses on practice outcomes: A systematic review using the kirkpatrick evaluation model	Helen Cope and Karen Campbell	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Augmented reality simulation-based training for midwifery students and its impact on perceived knowledge, confidence and skills for managing critical incidents	Kristina Vogel and Annette Bernloehr and Tabea Willmeroth and Jonas Blattgerste and Claudia Hellmers and Nicola H. Bauer	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Integration of Information Technology in Educational Practices:	Sandy I Ching Wang and Chih Fei Hsieh and Ji-Yun Pai and Eric Zhi-Feng Liu	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Blended learning in entrepreneurship education: a systematic literature review	Christoph Viebig	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
How We Evaluate Postgraduate Medical E-Learning: Systematic Review	Robert {de Leeuw} and Anneloes {de Soet} and Sabine {van der Horst} and Kieran Walsh and Michiel Westerman and Fedde Scheele	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Technological innovations in layperson CPR education – A scoping review	Abigail E. Schipper and Charles S.M. Sloane and Lydia B. Shimelis and Ryan T. Kim	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Enhancing elementary school students' computational thinking and programming learning with graphic organizers	Tzu-Chi Yang and Zhi-Shen Lin	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Games, Virtual Environments, Mobile Applications and a Futurist's Crystal Ball	Eric B. Bauman	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected

Digital Education for Health Professionals: An Evidence Map, Conceptual Framework, and Research Agenda	Lorraine {Tudor Car} and Selina Poon and Bhone Myint Kyaw and David A Cook and Victoria Ward and Rifat Atun and Azeem Majeed and Jamie Johnston and Rianne M J J {van der Kleij} and Mariam Molokhia and Florian {V Wangenheim} and Martin Lupton and Niels Chavannes and Onyema Ajuebor and Charles G Prober and Josip Car	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effect of the "Prediction-observation-quiz-explanation" inquiry-based e-learning model on flow experience in green energy learning	Jon-Chao Hong and Chi-Ruei Tsai and Hsien-Sheng Hsiao and Po-Hsi Chen and Kuan-Cheng Chu and Jianjun Gu and Jirarat Sitthiworachart	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Combating cyberbullying in Thai youth: Learning innovation as a possible solution	Kantita Sripa and Phonraphee Thummaphan and Theeravut Ninphet and Veerapol Gulabutr	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Evaluating the User Interface and Usability Approaches for E-Learning Systems	Jehad Saad Alqurni	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Interventions to develop clinical judgment among nurses: A systematic review with narrative synthesis	Maite Mendivil-Pérez and Ana Choperena and Vanesa Salas and Mayte Chocarro-Haro and Cristina Oroviogicoechea	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Enhancing workplace e-learning with branching scenarios: an action case study	Ceri Pimblett and Lisa Rowe and Alex Fenton	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Teaching clinical skills online in pharmacy education: a scoping review	Lailaturrahmi Lailaturrahmi and Suzanne Caliph and Thao Vu and Ian Larson	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Child-home interaction: Design and usability evaluation of a game-based end-user development for children	Zahra Kakavand and Ali Asghar Nazari Shirehjini and Majid Ghosian Moghaddam and Shervin Shirmohammadi	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
A review on effective approach to teaching computer programming to undergraduates in developing countries	Idongesit Eteng and Sylvia Akpotuzor and Solomon O. Akinola and Iwinosa Agbonlahor	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Mobile augmented reality techniques with gamification to enhance learnability for higher institute students of chemistry course	Entisar Alhadi {Al Ghawail} and Sadok {Ben Yahia}	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Augmented reality mobile app development for all	José Miguel Mota and Iván Ruiz-Rube and Juan Manuel Dodero and Inmaculada Arnedillo-Sánchez	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Using real-time process data of domain-specific learning processes to provide adaptive support for learning and instruction: Challenges and opportunities	Roger Azevedo	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected

Emergency Online Programming Classes:	Su Ting Yong and Peter Gates	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Generative artificial intelligence for management education: applications, benefits, challenges and future research directions	Sreevatsa Bellary and Sobhan Sarkar and Arindra Nath Mishra	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Teaching to teach with technology - a project to encourage take-up of advanced technology in education	Orazio Miglino and Richard Walker	2010	Science@Direct	Rejected
Virtual Tool for the Development of Strategies to Reduce the Stress in Students	Leticia A. Neira Tovar and Angélica Quiroga and Francisco Torres	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Digital Education for the Management of Chronic Wounds in Health Care Professionals: Protocol for a Systematic Review by the Digital Health Education Collaboration	Laura Martinengo and Natalie Jia Ying Yeo and Zheng Qiang Tang and Kasturi D/O Markandran and Bhone Myint Kyaw and Lorainne {Tudor Car}	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
FriendZi: Piloting a game based curriculum for elementary students' social-emotional wellbeing	Manisha Nagpal and Sophia Shieh and Michael Maryniak and Anthony Carbone and Kara Carola	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Accounting education literature review (2019)	Barbara Apostolou and Jack W. Dorminey and John M. Hassell	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Combating school bullying through multi-role experience-based virtual scenario learning model: Assessing empathy, problem-solving, and self-efficacy from a multi-stakeholder perspective	Kai-Hsiang Yang and Yi Lu	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Visual programming languages integrated across the curriculum in elementary school: A two year case study using "Scratch" in five schools	José-Manuel Sáez-López and Marcos Román-González and Esteban Vázquez-Cano	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
Applying an online game-based formative assessment in a flowchart-based intelligent tutoring system for improving problem-solving skills	Danial Hooshyar and Rodina Binti Ahmad and Moslem Yousefi and Moein Fathi and Shi-Jinn Horng and Heuseok Lim	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Digital Game and School-Based Intervention for Students in Hong Kong: Quasi-Experimental Design	Angie KY Shum and Eliza SY Lai and Wing Gi Leung and Mabel NS Cheng and Ho Kit Wong and Sam WK So and Yik Wa Law and Paul SF Yip	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Going viral – capacity strengthening in the context of pandemic(s)	Tracey A. Mills and Sabina Wakasiaka and Elizabeth Ayebare and Valentina Actis Danna and Tina Lavender and Carol Bedwell	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Battling gender stereotypes: A user study of a code-learning game, "Code Combat," with middle school children	Yeliz Yücel and Kerem Rızvanoğlu	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effectiveness of educational interventions on thinking and operational skills in complex learning—A meta-analysis	Haoxin Xu and Tianrun Deng and Xianlong Xu and Xiaoqing Gu	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
ChatGPT affordance for logic learning strategies and its usefulness for developing knowledge and quality of logic in English argumentative writing	Ruofei Zhang and Di Zou and Gary Cheng	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected

Evolution, topics and relevant research methodologies in business intelligence and data analysis in the academic management of higher education institutions. A literature review	M. Correa-Peralta and J. Vinueza-Martínez and L. Castillo-Heredia	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Enhancing Computational Thinking Capability of Preschool Children by Game-based Smart Toys	Szu-Yin Lin and Shih-Yi Chien and Chia-Lin Hsiao and Chih-Hsien Hsia and Kuo-Ming Chao	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
FishTank.jl: A model-driven approach to gamified scientific modeling and visualization in Julia	Jake W. Liu	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Use of virtual games for interactive learning in a pharmacy curriculum	Jerika T. Lam and Mary A. Gutierrez and Jeff A. Goad and Larisa Odessky and Jason Bock	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Digital games and literacies	Jennifer Jenson and Danielle Burrell-Kim	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Smartphone Apps for Learning Progress and Course Revision* *This work was funded by Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germanys Excellence Strategy - EXC 2075 - 390740016. The authors thank the International Max Planck Research School for Intelligent Systems (IMPRS-IS) for supporting Anne Koch and Patricia Pauli. For correspondence, feedback or collaborations, contact patricia.pauli@ist.uni-stuttgart.de	Patricia Pauli and Anne Koch and Frank Allgöwer	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effect of generative artificial intelligence (AI)-based tool use on students' computational thinking skills, programming self-efficacy and motivation	Ramazan Yilmaz and Fatma Gizem {Karaoglan Yilmaz}	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
An analysis of football coaching education: A call to action	Nuno André Nunes and Grégory Hallé Petiot	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Analysis of interactive impact and student behavior of teaching online courses based on gamified learning	Xiujuan Yuan and Qiang Zheng	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Effectiveness of a Theory- and Web-Based Adaptive Implementation Intervention on Nurses' and Nursing Students' Intentions to Provide Brief Counseling: Protocol for a Randomized Controlled Trial	Guillaume Fontaine and Sylvie Cossette and Marie-Pierre Gagnon and Véronique Dubé and José Côté	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Prosocial digital games for youth: A systematic review of interventions	Pamela Saleme and Bo Pang and Timo Dietrich and Joy Parkinson	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Developing behavioral project management competencies – the generation footprint	Ivana Kužet and Marija Todorović and Mateja Manojlović and Ronggui Ding and Ivana Kovačević and Vladimir Obradovic	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Developing social-emotional concepts for learning with video games	Weimin Toh and David Kirschner	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Tracing a Little for Big Improvements: Application of Learning Analytics and Videogames for Student Assessment	Ángel Serrano-Laguna and Javier Torrente and Pablo Moreno-Ger and Baltasar Fernández-Manjón	2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
PlayMINT—an effective digital learning game for leadership competencies of female STEM students	Ilse Hagerer	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Learning game for training child bicyclists' situation awareness	Esko Lehtonen and Heidi Sahlberg and Emilia Rovamo and Heikki Summala	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected

Design fit in gamified online programming learning environment	Wei-Tsong Wang and Mega Kartika Sari	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
A gamified collaborative course in entrepreneurship: Focus on objectives and tools	Alessandra Antonaci and Francesca Maria Dagnino and Michela Ott and Francesco Bellotti and Riccardo Berta and Alessandro {De Gloria} and Elisa Lavagnino and Margarida Romero and Mireia Usart and Igor Mayer	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Is game-based language learning general or specific-oriented? Exploring the applicability of mobile virtual realities to medical English education in the middle east	Ali Derakhshan and Timothy Teo and Saeed Khazaie	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Developing computational thinking skills in higher education through peer reflection on robotics and programming exercises with Bee-Bots, Lego Mindstorms EV3 and Minecraft Education	Satu-Maarit Korte and Minna Körkkö and Line Reichelt Føreland	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Application of a serious-game-based blended learning approach for acute pulmonary embolism training among thoracic surgery nurses: A quasi-experimental study	Wang Anlong and Fang Ting and Luo Yiting and Xu Hui and Yan Yanyan and Liang Guanmian	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
A study on EMBA students' cognitive and decision-making models in learning through play	Ya-Cing Jhan and Pin Luarn and Hong-Wen Lin	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Serious game for programming in higher education	Thomas Hainey and Gavin Baxter	2024	Science@Direct	Accepted
Learning Programming at the Computational Thinking Level via Digital Game-Play	Cagin Kazimoglu and Mary Kiernan and Liz Bacon and Lachlan MacKinnon	2012	Science@Direct	Accepted
The design and evaluation of an AR-based serious game to teach programming	Vandit Sharma and Kaushal Kumar Bhagat and Huai-Hsuan Huang and Nian-Shing Chen	2022	Science@Direct	Accepted
Learning Basic Programming Concepts by Creating Games with Scratch Programming Environment	Ibrahim Ouahbi and Fatiha Kaddari and Hassane Darhmaoui and Abdelrhani Elachqar and Soufiane Lahmine	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Office Madness: Investigating the impact of a game using a real life job and programming scenario on player experience and perceived short-term learning	Stelios Xinogalos and Savvas Eleftheriadis	2023	Science@Direct	Accepted
Serious games in tertiary education: A case study concerning the comprehension of basic concepts in computer language implementation courses	Daniel Rodríguez-Cerezo and Antonio Sarasa-Cabezuelo and Mercedes Gómez-Albarrán and José-Luis Sierra	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
DVRT: Design and evaluation of a virtual reality drone programming teaching system	Zean Jin and Yulong Bai and Wei Song and Qinghe Yu and Xiaoxin Yue and Xiang Jia	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Enhancing SQL Learning: Gamified tutorials and flipped classroom synergy	Sandor Kiraly and Tamas Balla and Dora Kiraly and Geoffrey Vaughan	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
The landscape of research on the use of digital game-based learning apps to nurture creativity among young children: A review	Najmeh Behnamnia and Amirrudin Kamsin and Maizatul Akmar Binti Ismail	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Analysis of dynamic decision making underpinning supply chain resilience: A serious game approach	Tomomi Nonaka and Kentaro Miki and Ryo Odajima and Hajime Mizuyama	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected

The landscape of Block-based programming: Characteristics of block-based environments and how they support the transition to text-based programming	Yuhan Lin and David Weintrop	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effects of dynamic and static feedback under tasks with different difficulty levels in digital game-based learning	Peipei Mao and Zihui Cai and Zhikeng Wang and Xin Hao and Xitao Fan and Xiaojun Sun	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Strategies to improve student engagement in online nursing education: A systematic review	Sabrina Elias and Kathryn Taylor and Emerald Jenkins and Kelley Robinson and Yordanos Tesfai and Hae-Ra Han	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Development and evaluation of serious games for diagnosis and cognitive improvement of patients with mild cognitive impairment: A study protocol	Farveh Sabermahani and Mostafa Almasi-Dooghaee and Abbas Sheikhtaheri	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Assessing the benefits of gamification in mathematics for student gameful experience and gaming motivation	Dorit Alt	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Effects of a concept mapping-based two-tier test strategy on students' digital game-based learning performances and behavioral patterns	Feng-Ying Li and Gwo-Jen Hwang and Pei-Ying Chen and Yu-Jung Lin	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Serious Games in Surgical Medical Education: A Virtual Emergency Department as a Tool for Teaching Clinical Reasoning to Medical Students	Seung-Hun Chon and Ferdinand Timmermann and Thomas Dratsch and Nikolai Schuelper and Patrick Plum and Felix Berth and Rabi Raj Datta and Christoph Schramm and Stefan Haneder and Martin Richard Späth and Martin Dübbers and Julia Kleinert and Tobias Raupach and Christiane Bruns and Robert Kleinert	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Comparison Between Serious Games and Learning Version of Existing Games	Mohamed Ali Khenissi and Fathi Essalmi and Mohamed Jemni	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Unlocking competence, cultivating connections: Adapting escape rooms for graduate nursing education	Holly Stith and Andrew Makowski and Julie Perry	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Serious games and learning effectiveness: The case of It's a Deal!	Victoria Guillén-Nieto and Marian Aleson-Carbonell	2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
A systematic mapping study on game-related methods for software engineering education	Mauricio R. de A. Souza and Lucas Veado and Renata Teles Moreira and Eduardo Figueiredo and Heitor Costa	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Computer Games: Implementation into Teaching and Learning	Ibrahim Ahmad and Azizah Jaafar	2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Serious Game for Enhancing Rescue Reasoning Skills in Tactical Combat Casualty Care: Development and Deployment Study	Siyue Zhu and Zenan Li and Ying Sun and Linghui Kong and Ming Yin and Qinge Yong and Yuan Gao	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Do technological knowledge and game-based learning promote students achievement: lesson from Indonesia	Cipto Wardoyo and Yogi Dwi Satrio and Bagus Shandy Narmaditya and Agus Wibowo	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected

The reality of the gamification methodology in Primary Education: A systematic review	José-María Romero-Rodríguez and Alejandro Martínez-Menéndez and Santiago Alonso-García and Juan-José Victoria-Maldonado	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effects of CS-unplugged activities integrated into traditional street games on block-based coding performance of students	Sati Karaca-Durmuşkaya and Emine Şendurur	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Formative evaluation of immersive virtual reality expedition mini-games to facilitate computational thinking	Amos Sunday Oyelere and Friday Joseph Agbo and Solomon Sunday Oyelere	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Designing a Course for Stimulating Entrepreneurship in Higher Education through Serious Games	F. Bellotti and R. Berta and A. {De Gloria} and E. Lavagnino and F. Dagnino and M. Ott and M. Romero and M. Usart and I.S. Mayer	2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
A blocks-based serious game to support introductory computer programming in undergraduate education	Adilson Vahldick and Paulo Roberto Farah and Maria José Marcelino and António José Mendes	2020	Science@Direct	Accepted
Gamification and Game-Based Strategies for Dermatology Education: Narrative Review	Mindy D Szeto and Daniel Strock and Jarett Anderson and Torunn E Sivesind and Victoria M Vorwald and Hope R Rietcheck and Gil S Weintraub and Robert P Dellavalle	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials on the effect of serious games on people with dementia	Ita Daryanti Saragih and Gauthier Everard and Bih-O Lee	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Serious Game for Developing Computational Thinking and Learning Introductory Computer Programming	Cagin Kazimoglu and Mary Kiernan and Liz Bacon and Lachlan Mackinnon	2012	Science@Direct	Accepted
Thriving in the era of hybrid work: Raising cybersecurity awareness using serious games in industry trainings	Tiange Zhao and Tiago Gasiba and Ulrike Lechner and Maria Pinto-Albuquerque	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Game-based learning approach on students' motivation and understanding of chemistry concepts: A systematic review of literature	Edwin Byusa and Edwige Kampire and Adrian Rwekaza Mwesigye	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
A mini-flipped, game-based Mediterranean diet learning program on dietary behavior and cognitive function among community-dwelling older adults in Taiwan: A cluster-randomized controlled trial	Cheng-Chen Chou and Yu-Jen Li and Chi-Jane Wang and Li-Ching Lyu	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Development of Serious Games (Equit'Game) to Address Health and Environmental Inequalities: Protocol for an App-Delivered Program to Perform a Territorial Diagnosis	Wahida {Kihal Talantikite} and Damien Renou and Arnold Magdelaine and William Harang and Denis Zmirou-Navier and Severine Deguen	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Hybrid Escape Room to Foster Motivation and Programming Education for Pre-Service Teachers	Oriol Borrás-Gené and Raquel Hijón-Neira and Pedro Paredes-Barragán and Lucía Serrano-Luján	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Evaluation of affective embodied agents in an information literacy game	Yan Ru Guo and Dion Hoe-Lian Goh	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected

An evaluation of the introduction of games-based construction learning in upper primary education using a developed game codification scheme for scratch	Thomas Hainey and Gavin Baxter and Amanda Ford	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
"Giant Leap 1": A Social and Emotional Learning program's effects on the transition to first grade	Karla Correia and Alexandra Marques-Pinto	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
Building a Comprehensive R&D Community on Serious Games	A. {De Gloria} and F. Bellotti and R. Berta	2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
Uses and Gratifications approach to evaluate the continuance intention of ATIC: A serious video game to learn entrepreneurship	Esteban Crespo-Martínez and Salvador Bueno and M. Dolores Gallego	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Digital Game-Based Learning effectiveness assessment: Reflections on study design	Anissa All and Elena Nuñez Patricia Castellar and Jan {Van Looy}	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effect of using community-based learning program in science students' achievement according to Kolb's learning styles	Abdel-Ghani Saifi and Zuhair N. Khlaif and Saida Affouneh	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Teacher perceptions of the value of game-based learning in secondary education	J.C. Huizenga and G.T.M. {ten Dam} and J.M. Voogt and W.F. Admiraal	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Constructionist visions: Hard fun with serious games	Yasmin B. Kafai	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
ADRENALINE, a Learning Game to Improve Prescribing Skills in Undergraduate Medical Students: Descriptive Study	Cecile Marie Yelnik and Aurélie Daumas and Yanele Poteaux and Annie Standaert and Natacha Grimbert and Raphaël Favory and Pierre Ravaux and Marc Lambert and Katia Quelenec	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Soft skills in personnel training: Report of publications in scopus, topics explored and future research agenda	Lorena C. Espina-Romero and Sandra Lucia {Aguirre Franco} and Helga Ofelia {Dworaczek Conde} and Jesús M. Guerrero-Alcedo and Doile Enrique {Ríos Parra} and Juan Carlos {Rave Ramírez}	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 4 - Toward emotionally intelligent interfaces: An HCI approach to cognitive and learning support	Prabhat Kumar and Arie Kurnianto and Nitin Sahai	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Self-Adaptive Serious Game to Improve Motor Learning Among Older Adults in Immersive Virtual Reality: Short-Term Longitudinal Pre-Post Study on Retention and Transfer	Gauthier Everard and Louise Declerck and Thierry Lejeune and Martin Gareth Edwards and Justine Bogacki and Cléo Reiprich and Kelly Delvigne and Nicolas Legrain and Charles Sebiyo Batcho	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Cybersecurity Enhancement through Blockchain Training (CEBT) – A serious game approach	Ansh Mittal and M.P. Gupta and Manmohan Chaturvedi and Shailesh R. Chansarkar and Sameer Gupta	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Exploring player agency in educational video games	Amogh Joshi and Christos Mousas and Samin Shahriar Tokey and Dominic Kao	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected

The effectiveness of gamification in programming education: Evidence from a meta-analysis	Zehui Zhan and Luyao He and Yao Tong and Xinya Liang and Shihao Guo and Xixin Lan	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Narrating professional development trajectories in the context of the Statecraft X game-based learning curriculum	Swati Mehrotra and Yam San Chee and Jing Chuan Ong	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effective components of creativity in digital game-based learning among young children: A case study	Najmeh Behnamnia and Amirrudin Kamsin and Maizatul Akmar Binti Ismail and A. Hayati	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Game-based learning approach in computer science in primary education: A systematic review	Maja Videnovik and Ana {Madevska Bogdanova} and Vladimir Trajkovik	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Synthesis of nested loop exercises for practice in introductory programming	Chinedu Wilfred Okonkwo and Abejide Ade-Ibijola	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Virtual Emergency Telemedicine Serious Game in Medical Training: A Quantitative, Professional Feedback-Informed Evaluation Study	Iolie Nicolaidou and Athos Antoniadis and Riana Constantinou and Charis Marangos and Efthymou Kyriacou and Panagiotis Bamidis and Eleni Dafli and Constantinos S Pattichis	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Emerging educational technologies: Tensions and synergy	J. Michael Spector	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
BeadLoom Game: using game elements to increase motivation and learning	Boyce, Acey and Barnes, Tiffany	2010	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Motivation, Optimal Experience and Flow in First Year Computing Science	McDermott, Roger and Zarb, Mark and Daniels, Mats and Cajander, \r{A}sa and Clear, Tony	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
The Pedagogical Potential of Game Jams	Fowler, Allan and Ni, Xuelei (Sherry) and Preston, Jon	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
UbiPlay: an interactive playground and visual programming tools for children	Mattila, Jussi and \V{a}n{a}n{e}n, Antti	2006	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Comprehension-First Pedagogy and Adaptive, Intrinsically Motivated Tutorials	Nelson, Greg L.	2017	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Chinese CHI '22: Proceedings of the Tenth International Symposium of Chinese CHI		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Ingenium: Engaging Novice Students with Latin Grammar	Zhou, Sharon and Livingston, Ivy J. and Schiefsky, Mark and Shieber, Stuart M. and Gajos, Krzysztof Z.	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Digispired: digital inspiration for interactive game design and programming	Javidi, Giti and Sheybani, Ehsan	2009	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
The Game Genre Map: A Revised Game Classification	Heintz, Stephanie and Law, Effie Lai-Chong	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Securing the Human: A Review of Literature on Broadening Diversity in Cybersecurity Education	Mountroidou, Xenia and Vosen, David and Kari, Chadi and Azhar, Mohammad Q. and Bhatia, Sajal and Gagne, Greg and Maguire, Joseph and Tudor, Liviana and Yuen, Timothy T.	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
EKI '25: Proceedings of the 2025 3rd International Conference on Educational Knowledge and Informatization		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Exploring the Purpose and Development of Academic Games: An Analysis of Games Reported at the Foundations of Digital Games Conference (2007–2024)	Chen, Max and Morrell, Edward	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Mobile location-based games to support orientation & mobility training for visually impaired students	Regal, Georg and Mattheiss, Elke and Sellitsch, David and Tscheligi, Manfred	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Design and First Results of a Psychometric Test for Measuring Basic Programming Abilities	Mühling, Andreas and Ruf, Alexander and Hubwieser, Peter	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
FDG '22: Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on the Foundations of Digital Games		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
New Horizons in the Assessment of Computer Science at School and Beyond: Leveraging on the ViVA Platform	Giordano, Daniela and Maiorana, Francesco and Csizmadia, Andrew Paul and Marsden, Simon and Riedesel, Charles and Mishra, Shitanshu and Vinikienundefined, Lina	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
On the Role of Design in K-12 Computing Education	Oleson, Alannah and Wortzman, Brett and Ko, Amy J.	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Game Development for Computer Science Education	Johnson, Chris and McGill, Monica and Bouchard, Durell and Bradshaw, Michael K. and Bucheli, Victor A. and Merkle, Laurence D. and Scott, Michael James and Sweedyk, Z. and Velázquez-Iturbide, J. Ángel and Xiao, Zhiping and Zhang, Ming	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
The education arcade: crafting, remixing, and playing with controllers for Scratch games	Davis, Richard and Kafai, Yasmin and Vasudevan, Veena and Lee, Eunkyong	2013	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Informing Content-driven Design of Computer Programming Games: a Problems Analysis and a Game Review	Laporte, Lieve and Zaman, Bieke	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Virtual Reality-Based, Gamified Accessibility Education: An Experience Report	Aljedaani, Wajdi and Parthasarathy, P D and Tong, Xin and Zhou, Kyrie Zhixuan	2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICDEL '24: Proceedings of the 2024 9th International Conference on Distance Education and Learning		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
The Role of Learning Theory in Child-Computer Interaction - A Semi-Systematic Literature Review	Eriksson, Eva and Baykal, Gökcü Elif and Torgersson, Olof	2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

The study of gamification application architecture for programming language course	Khaleel, Firas Layth and Ashaari, Noraidah Sahari@ and Meriam, Tengku Siti and Wook, Tengku and Ismail, Amirah	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Towards social gaming methods for improving game-based computer science education	Hicks, Andrew	2010	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Does text-based programming improve K-12 students' CT skills? Evidence from a meta-analysis and synthesis of qualitative data in educational contexts	Lihui Sun and Liang Zhou	2023	Science@Direct	Accepted
Tangibles vs. Mouse in Educational Programming Games: Influences on Enjoyment and Self-Beliefs	Melcer, Edward F. and Hollis, Victoria and Isbister, Katherine	2017	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Integrating Computational Thinking into the Process of Learning Artificial Intelligence	Shih, Wen-Chung	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CSERC '22: Proceedings of the 11th Computer Science Education Research Conference		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICFET '24: Proceedings of the 2024 10th International Conference on Frontiers of Educational Technologies		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Are libraries ready to serve gamification tools for teaching and learning? A review based on computational mapping	Swagota Saikia and Sumeer Gul and Manoj Kumar Verma	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Serious game training improves performance in combat life-saving interventions	Jerome Planchon and Anthony Vacher and Jeremy Comblet and Eric Rabatel and Françoise Darses and Alexandre Mignon and Pierre Pasquier	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Experimental evaluation of teaching recursion in a video game	Chaffin, Amanda and Doran, Katelyn and Hicks, Drew and Barnes, Tiffany	2009	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Instructors' Perspectives on Capstone Courses in Computing Fields: A Mixed-Methods Study	Hooshangi, Sara and Shakil, Asma and Dasgupta, Subhasish and C. Davis, Karen C. and Farghally, Mohammed and Fitzpatrick, KellyAnn and Gutica, Mirela and Hardt, Ryan and Riddle, Steve and Seyam, Mohammed	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
A Hands-On Cybersecurity Curriculum Using a Robotics Platform	Yett, Bernard and Hutchins, Nicole and Stein, Gordon and Zare, Hamid and Snyder, Caitlin and Biswas, Gautam and Metelko, Mary and L'eczi, Akos	2020	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SA '24: SIGGRAPH Asia 2024 Educator's Forum		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Augmented Reality and programming education: A systematic review	Anastasios Theodoropoulos and George Lepouras	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Evaluation of games for teaching computer science	Gibson, Ben and Bell, Tim	2013	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Noisruer: A Student-developed Game for Recursion	Bakken, Nora and Gonzales, Geoffrey and Jimenez, Osvaldo	2025	ACM Digital Library	Accepted

Software visualisation through video games	Marques, Bradley R. C. and Levitt, Stephen P. and Nixon, Ken J.	2012	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Training disaster communication by means of serious games in virtual environments	Nina Haferkamp and Nicole C. Kraemer and Conor Linehan and Massimiliano Schembri	2011	Science@Direct	Rejected
An Investigation into Students' Motivation and Learning Effectiveness in Gamified Learning Experiences via Kahoot! at a Higher Education Institution in Vietnam	Thi Van Pham, Anh and Thi Thao Ho, Nguyen and Duy Nguyen, Ly	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Challenging stereotypes and changing attitudes: the effect of a brief programming encounter on adults' attitudes toward programming	Charters, Polina and Lee, Michael J. and Ko, Amy J. and Loksa, Dastyni	2014	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Exploring the co-manipulation of physical and virtual objects in tangible mobile augmented reality for collaborative learning	Gardeli, Anna and Vosinakis, Spyros	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Implementing the jigsaw model in CS1 closed labs	Soh, Leen-Kiat	2006	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
DevCoach: Supporting Students Learning the Software Development Life Cycle with a Generative AI powered Multi-Agent System	Wang, Tianjia and Trimble, Matthew and Brown, Chris	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Microlearning-Inspired Approach for Teaching Business Modeling to Computer Engineering Students	Popgeorgiev, Angel and Ibryamova, Eliisa and Ivanova, Galina	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
The computational puzzle design framework: a design guide for games teaching computational thinking	Jiang, Xina and Hartevelde, Casper and Huang, Xinyuan and Fung, Anthony Y. H.	2019	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Cybersecurity Education in the Age of AI: Integrating AI Learning into Cybersecurity High School Curricula	Grover, Shuchi and Broll, Brian and Babb, Derek	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Scaffolding Novices: Analyzing When and How Parsons Problems Impact Novice Programming in an Integrated Science Assignment	Tabarsi, Benyamin and Reichert, Heidi and Lytle, Nicholas and Catete, Veronica and Barnes, Tiffany	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
AIEE '25: Proceedings of the 2025 International Conference on AI-enabled Education		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
After-Hours Learning: Workshops for Professional Women to Learn Web Development	Peñalva, Joslenne and Hanrahan, Benjamin V. and Rosson, Mary Beth and Cole, Carmen	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Progression Trajectory-Based Student Modeling for Novice Block-Based Programming	Morshed Fahid, Fahmid and Tian, Xiaoyi and Emerson, Andrew and B. Wiggins, Joseph and Bounajim, Dolly and Smith, Andy and Wiebe, Eric and Mott, Bradford and Elizabeth Boyer, Kristy and Lester, James	2021	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Emerging Advanced Technologies for Game Engineering	Arnedo-Moreno, Joan and Cooper, Kendra M. L. and Lin, Dayi	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Designing hybrid and XR narrative applications: a framework to describe authoring tools in cultural domain	M. Massidda and L. Travaglini and S. Pescarin	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Motivational active learning: engaging university students in computer science education	Pirker, Johanna and Riffnaller-Schiefer, Maria and Gützl, Christian	2014	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Scaling Up Collaborative Dialogue Analysis: An AI-driven Approach to Understanding Dialogue Patterns in Computational Thinking Education	Yin, Stella Xin and Liu, Zhengyuan and Goh, Dion Hoe-Lian and Quek, Choon Lang and Chen, Nancy F.	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
MoonBase VR: Learning to program in a virtual reality game	Holder, Raymond and Carey, Mark and Walder, Patrick and Keir, Paul	2023	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Designing and comparing two scratch-based teaching approaches for students aged 10--12 years	van Es, Nienke and Jeuring, Johan	2017	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Effectiveness of Video-based Training for Face-to-face Communication Skills of Software Engineers: Evidence from a Three-year Study	Mitrovic, Antonija and Galster, Matthias and Malinen, Sanna and Holland, Jay and Musa, Ja'afaru and Mohammadhassan, Negar and Lumapas, Raul Vincent	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICEEL '22: Proceedings of the 2022 6th International Conference on Education and E-Learning		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
GROUP '25: Companion Proceedings of the 2025 ACM International Conference on Supporting Group Work		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHI PLAY Companion '25: Companion Proceedings of the Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Broadening participation through scalable game design	Repenning, Alexander and Ioannidou, Andri	2008	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ScriptAR: No-Code Development of Augmented Reality Educational Games	Holford, Robert and Wales, Michaelah and Kelly, Lindsey J. and Bednarski, Steven and Bullock, Alison and Harrap, Robin and MacDonald, Zack and Graham, T.C. Nicholas	2025	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Measuring learning and fun in video games for young children: a proposed method	Fowler, Allan	2013	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Instructional design as game design	Bayliss, Jessica D. and Schwartz, David I.	2009	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Designing Designer: The Evidence-Oriented Design Process of a Pedagogical Interactive Graphics Python Library	Holsapple, Kristina and Bart, Austin Cory	2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Active Learning through Game Play in a Data Structures Course	Dicheva, Darina and Hodge, Austin	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
TeachVR: An Immersive Virtual Reality Framework for Computational Thinking Based on Student Preferences	Wee, Chyanna and Wang, Lillian Yee Kiaw and Ong, Huey Fang	2025	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Real Exploits Driven Cybersecurity Modules for Cross-Module Learning and Security Mindset Building	Li, Yanyan and Hernandez, David and Yuan, Jiawei	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
A Tangible Embedded Programming System to Convey Event-Handling Concept	Wang, Danli and Zhang, Lan and Xu, Chao and Hu, Haichen and Qi, Yunfeng	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Using scalable game design to teach computer science from middle school to graduate school	Basawapatna, Ashok R. and Koh, Kyu Han and Repenning, Alexander	2010	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Towards Understanding the Impact of AI-Generated Visual and Vocal Self-Similarity on Avatar Identification, Motivation, and Engagement in Educational Games	Shao, Tianyu and Oyedokun, Olaoluwa and Mousas, Christos and Kao, Dominic	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Learning to Program with Personal Robots: Influences on Student Motivation	McGill, Monica M.	2012	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Machineers: playfully introducing programming to children	Lode, Henrike and Franchi, Giuseppe E. and Frederiksen, Niels G.	2013	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Fostering High School Girls' Interest and Attainment in Computer Science	Gutica, Mirela	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Ordered Network Analysis in CS Education: Unveiling Patterns of Success and Struggle in Automated Programming Assessment	Zambrano, Andres Felipe and Pankiewicz, Maciej and Barany, Amanda and Baker, Ryan S.	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Predictive Student Modeling in Block-Based Programming Environments with Bayesian Hierarchical Models	Emerson, Andrew and Geden, Michael and Smith, Andy and Wiebe, Eric and Mott, Bradford and Boyer, Kristy Elizabeth and Lester, James	2020	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Introducing Blockchains at School Without Computers: Hands-On Sense-Making for Young Learners	Pellegrino, Maria Angela and Guasti, Lorenzo	2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
The Effects of Adaptive Procedural Levels on Engagement and Performance in an Educational Programming Game	Jemmali, Chaima and Seif El-Nasr, Magy and Cooper, Seth	2022	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Gamification of Learning as a Supplementary Learning Support for Mapua IT Students	Rey, William P. and Serrano, Elcid A. and Alfonso, Adrian B. and Funilas, John Ramil F. and Huplo, Kiel Cedrick T.	2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Enhancing Computer Science Education with Adaptive Serious Games	Miljanovic, Michael Alexander	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Investigating the Interaction of Game Features and Spatial Skills with Performance and Perceived Difficulty in a Block-Based 3D Programming Puzzle Game	Rajapaksha, Yasitha and Thomas Bacher, John and Barnes, Tiffany	2026	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Understanding Learning Curves and Trajectories in CSS Layout	Kim, Meen Chul and Park, Thomas H. and Liu, Ruixue and Forte, Andrea	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Evaluation of a game-based lab assignment	Eagle, Michael and Barnes, Tiffany	2009	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
How can a social debugging game effectively teach computer programming concepts?	Lee, Michael J.	2013	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
SQL-Wordle: Gamification of SQL Programming Exercises	Ambasana, Jatin and Sahasrabudhe, Sameer and Iyer, Sridhar	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
A Systematic Literature Review of Automated Feedback Generation for Programming Exercises	Keuning, Hieke and Jeurig, Johan and Heeren, Bastiaan	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Supporting Pharmaceutical Healthcare Outreach: A Culminating First-Year Programming Experience	Estell, John K. and Coffman-Wolph, Stephany and Sieg, Jessica and Musser, Michelle	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Investigating Structural Gamification as an Approach to Increase Student Engagement towards Practical Exercises in the Computer Science Topics	Ambasana, Jatin	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Using Commutative Assessments to Compare Conceptual Understanding in Blocks-based and Text-based Programs	Weintrop, David and Wilensky, Uri	2015	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
UKICER '25: Proceedings of the 2025 Conference on UK and Ireland Computing Education Research		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Designing Workshops to Bridge Visual and Textual Programming: A Narrative Game Approach	Matutat, Andr{e} and Franke, Benjamin and Schumann, Niklas and George, Birgit Christina and Keuntje, J{o}rg Michael and Gips, Carsten	2026	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Auto-generated game levels increase novice programmers' engagement	Lee, Michael J.	2020	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Game Development with a Serious Focus	Kletenik, Devorah and Sturm, Deborah	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Computational thinking in educational activities: an evaluation of the educational game light-bot	Gouws, Lindsey Ann and Bradshaw, Karen and Wentworth, Peter	2013	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Integrating parson's programming puzzles into a game-based mobile learning application	Oyelere, Solomon Sunday and Suhonen, Jarkko and Laine, Teemu H.	2017	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Towards a Framework for Teaching Debugging	Li, Chen and Chan, Emily and Denny, Paul and Luxton-Reilly, Andrew and Tempero, Ewan	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Teaching Foundational Programming to Young Learners via a Block Based Game	Gallacher, Marc and Imperatore, Gennaro	2025	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Challenging but Full of Opportunities: Teachers' Perspectives on Programming in Primary Schools	Greifenstein, Luisa and Gra{ss}l, Isabella and Fraser, Gordon	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
(Re)engaging novice online learners in an educational programming game	Lee, Michael J.	2020	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Animated hints help novices complete more levels in an educational programming game	Lee, Michael J. and Chiou, Joseph	2020	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Experimental evaluation of an educational game for improved learning in introductory computing	Eagle, Michael and Barnes, Tiffany	2009	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Dragon architect: open design problems for guided learning in a creative computational thinking sandbox game	Bauer, Aaron and Butler, Eric and Popovi{c}, Zoran	2017	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Multilingual Game Programming to Enhance Computational Thinking in CS0	Lee, Dongeun and El Ariss, Omar and Hu, Kaoning and Kwon, Kibum	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Digital Accessibility Education using Serious Games	Parthasarathy, P.D.	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
TurtleTalk: An Educational Programming Game for Children with Voice User Interface	Jung, Hyunhoon and Kim, Hee Jae and So, Seongeun and Kim, Jinjoong and Oh, Changhoon	2019	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Sorting the Universe: Learning Success and Perception of Flow in an Immersive Game for Training Sorting Algorithms	Unro, Daniel and Dengel, Andreas	2025	ACM Digital Library	Accepted

Programming in game space: how to represent parallel programming concepts in an educational game	Zhu, Jichen and Alderfer, Katelyn and Furqan, Anushay and Nebolsky, Jessica and Char, Bruce and Smith, Brian and Villareale, Jennifer and Ontalán, Santiago	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Robot on! a serious game for improving programming comprehension	Miljanovic, Michael A. and Bradbury, Jeremy S.	2016	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
AccessQuest: A Game-Based Approach to Digital Accessibility Education	Parthasarathy, P D and Joshi, Swaroop	2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Exploring the Impact of CodeCombat Python Programming Curriculum on Student Motivation at Primary School	Choi, Iek Chong and Choi, Wan Chong and Chang, Chi In	2025	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Experience with Dream Coders: developing a 2D RPG for teaching introductory programming concepts	Chang, Jack Keng-Wei and Dang, Long Hoang and Pavleas, Jebediah and McCarthy, Joseph F. and Sung, Kelvin and Bay, Jason	2012	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Game of Codes: Towards Learning Java by an Educational Mobile Game Adapted to Female Programming Novices	Eiband, Brian Jannik and Bergande, Bianca and Schedel, Angela and Brune, Philipp	2019	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Computational thinking and robotics in education	García-Peláez, Francisco José and Conde, Miguel A. and González-Alves, José and Lima, José	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
RoboBUG: A Serious Game for Learning Debugging Techniques	Miljanovic, Michael A. and Bradbury, Jeremy S.	2017	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Scaffolding CS1 Courses with a Large Language Model-Powered Intelligent Tutoring System	Cao, Chen	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Can Digital Game-Based Learning be incorporated in Serbian Primary School Curricula's?	Aleksić, Veljko and Ivanović, Mirjana	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Coding to Cope: Teaching Programming to Children with Emotional and Behavioral Disorders	Grassl, Isabella and Fraser, Gordon	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Exploring the Influence of Avatar Skin Tone in VR Educational Games	Oyedokun, Olaoluwa and Mubarrat, Syed Tanzim and Joshi, Amogh and Mousas, Christos and Kao, Dominic	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Supporting CS1 Instructors: Design and Evaluation of a Game Generator	Anyango, Jecton Tocho and Suleman, Hussein	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Designing Visual Metaphors for an Educational Game for Parallel Programming	Ontalán, Santiago and Zhu, Jichen and Smith, Brian K. and Char, Bruce and Freed, Evan and Furqan, Anushay and Howard, Michael and Nguyen, Anna and Patterson, Justin and Valls-Vargas, Josep	2017	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Circle of Life: Microworld Project at the End of CS1	Nicolajsen, Sebastian Mateos and Caspersen, Michael E. and Brabrand, Claus	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Educational game design: an empirical study of the effects of narrative	Jemmali, Chaima and Bunian, Sara and Mambretti, Andrea and El-Nasr, Magy Seif	2018	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
The Influence of CodeCombat on Computational Thinking in Python Programming Learning at Primary School	Choi, Wan Chong and Choi, Iek Chong	2024	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
2018 SIGCSE special project grants	Fitzgerald, Sue	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Students' Debugging Behavior Analysis in Game-Based Learning	Yang, Fan and Dong, Zhenghong and Wu, Zhongwang	2021	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Towards a Constructionist Serious Game Engine	Vahldick, Adilson and Mendes, Antonio Jos ^e and Marcelino, Maria Jos ^e	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CodeAdventure: Learning Introductory Programming	Nicou, Giorgos and Andreou, Panayiotis and Polycarpou, Irene	2017	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
ICSE-SEET '23: Proceedings of the 45th International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering Education and Training		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICETM '24: Proceedings of the 2024 7th International Conference on Educational Technology Management		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
The third ACM international workshop on multimedia technologies for distance learning (MTDL 2011)	Lau, Rynson W.H. and Shih, Timothy K. and Li, Frederick W.B. and Yen, Neil Y.	2011	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Association rule mining and visualization of introductory programming course activities	Matetic, Maja and Bakaric, Marija Brkic and Sisovic, Sabina	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
The Design Space of Turtle Graphics Tasks	Pel ^a nek, Radek	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Influence of the Programming Environment on Programming Education	Saito, Daisuke and Washizaki, Hironori and Fukazawa, Yoshiaki	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Game-based concept visualization for learning programming	Li, Frederick W.B. and Watson, Christopher	2011	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Using game design mechanics as metaphors to enhance learning of introductory programming concepts	Jemmali, Chaima and Kleinman, Erica and Bunian, Sara and Almeda, Mia Victoria and Rowe, Elizabeth and El-Nasr, Magy Seif	2019	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Program Wars v.2.0 : Improving a Game-based Learning Approach for Teaching Fundamental Programming Concepts	Tareque, Md. Hasan and Deutekom, Steven and Anvik, John and Bashir, Maimoona	2024	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
A Systematic Review of Computational Thinking Approach for Programming Education in Higher Education Institutions	Agbo, Friday Joseph and Oyelere, Solomon Sunday and Suhonen, Jarkko and Adewumi, Sunday	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Enhancing Informatics Education Through a Serious Game: Design, Development, and Pedagogical Impact	Gkini, Evgenia and Tsaousis, Panagiotis and Sgouropoulou, Cleo and Voyiatzis, Ioannis	2025	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Accessibility Education for Software Engineers: Evaluating the Impact of Game-Based Learning	Parthasarathy, P D and Joshi, Swaroop	2026	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Bug-eecha 2.0: An Educational Game for CS1 Students and Instructors	Joseph, Amrit M and Sarma, Soumyadeep and Shelly and Kumar, Viraj	2023	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Supporting Co-Regulation and Motivation in Learning Programming in Online Classrooms	Goswami, Lahari and Senges, Alexandre and Estier, Thibault and Cherubini, Mauro	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Introductory programming: a systematic literature review	Luxton-Reilly, Andrew and Simon and Albluwi, Ibrahim and Becker, Brett A. and Giannakos, Michail and Kumar, Amruth N. and Ott, Linda and Paterson, James and Scott, Michael James and Sheard, Judy and Szabo, Claudia	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Learning from Teachers: AI-Driven Feedback for a High School Python Serious Game	Branth ^o me, Matthieu and Lall ^e , S ^e bastien	2025	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Regulation of Learning Interventions in Programming Education: A Systematic Literature Review and Guideline Proposition	Silva, Leonardo and Mendes, Ant ^o nio Jos ^e and Gomes, Anabela and Cavalcanti de Mac ^e do, Gabriel Fortes	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Codeseum: Learning Introductory Programming Concepts through Virtual Reality Puzzles	Ekman, Johan and Solsona, Jordi and Quintero, Luis	2024	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Impact of Adaptive Feedback on Learning Programming with a Serious Game in High Schools' Classes	Branth ^o me, Matthieu and Lall ^e , S ^e bastien	2025	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Topical Analysis of Programming Education Research Literature	Malmi, Lauri and L ^o pez-Pernas, Sonsoles and Nguyen, Hung and Apiola, Mikko and Saqr, Mohammed	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Mobile Learning to Support Computational Thinking in Initial Teacher Education:	Cornelia Connolly and Raquel Hijón-Neira and Seán Ó Grádaigh	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
The role of the predictive gamification to increase the sales performance: a novel business approach	Elenise Martins Rocha and Giancarlo Medeiros Pereira and Diego Augusto de Jesus Pacheco	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
The effect of self-regulated programming learning on undergraduate students' academic performance and motivation	Mücahit Öztürk	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
28 - Medical Simulation in Disaster Preparedness	Vincent Bounes	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
A Game-Changing Instructor Tool to Reinforce Coding Concepts	Kletenic, Devorah and Sturm, Deborah	2020	ACM Digital Library	Accepted

The Synergy Approach: Technology-Enhanced Learning Across Key Stages in CS1	Jin, Wei and Park, Hyesung and Xu, Xin and Brannock, Evelyn and Im, Tacksoo and Leader, Tirza	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Testando a Diversão em um Jogo Sério para o Aprendizado Introdutório de Programação	Adilson Vahldick and Antônio Mendes and Maria Marcelino and Maciel Hogenn and Pablo Schoeffel	2015	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Accepted
Avaliação da Aplicação de Jogos no Ensino de Programação: Uma Experiência Em Uma Disciplina Introdutória	Paulo Renato Mendes and Pedro Vinícius Freitas and Kássio Romulo Sousa and Carlos Soares Neto	2018	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Accepted
Project Éden: platform for introductory programming concepts	Yure Oliveira and Claudio Toledo and Leonardo Pereira	2021	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Accepted
Extracting Learning Analytics from Lightbot Gameplay Sessions	Adriano Gil and Thiago Figueira and José Netto	2024	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Accepted
A Importância de Jogos Sérios na Aprendizagem de Programação	Anderson Araújo and Lauren Roma and Rodrigo Ramos and Willian Santos and Gilton Silva	2024	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Rejected
An Investigation into the Perception of Gen Z Students in Higher Education towards Gamification Techniques in Learning Computing Subjects	Chong, Mien May and Subramanian, Preethi and Ting, Mary and Ying, Lau Joe	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Useful recommendations for successful implementation of programming courses	Biñas, M. and Pietriková, E.	2014	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Automated Feedback and Authentic Assessment for Online Computational Thinking Tutoring Systems	Jamil, Hasan M. and Mou, Xin	2022	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Improving web-based problem solving skills of students with a novel game-based Intelligent Tutoring System	Hooshyar, Danial and Ahmad, Rodina Binti and Yousefi, Moslem and Fathi, Moein and Horng, Shi-Jinn and Hooshyar, Maral and Dooraki, Amir Ramezani	2015	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Learning by gaming - evaluation of an online game for children	Lazareck, Lisa J. and Farrell, David and Kostkova, Patty and Lecky, Donna M. and McNulty, Cliodna A. M. and Weerasinghe, Dasun	2010	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
A MicroPython-based Educational Robotic Maze Approach: Learning Improvement to Competition	Thanyaphongphat, Jirapipat and Thongkoo, Krittawaya and Daungcharone, Kannika	2023	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Cross platform interactive programming learning environment for kids with edutainment and gamification	Sarkar, Shubhra Prakash and Sarker, Biplab and Hossain, S.K. Alalmgir	2016	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted

Introductory Computer Programming Teaching and Learning Approaches: Review	Mbiada, Alain Kabo and Isong, Bassey and Lugayizi, Francis and Abu-Mahfouz, Adnan	2022	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Use of active methodologies for the development of a teaching plan for the algorithms subject	Da Silva Garcia, Fabrício Wickey and Da Costa Carvalho, Elielton and Bezerra Oliveira, Sandro Ronaldo	2021	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Learning Effects of Programming Educational Board Game in Collaborative Learning between Robots and Humanities Students	Inoue, Tomoki and Jimenez, Felix and Onuki, Mamoru	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
A game concept using conflictive animations for learning programming	Moreno, Andrés and Sutinen, Erkki and Islas Sedano, Carolina	2013	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Gamification of the Learning Process for Acquiring Logical Thinking in Programming	Barcan, Nicoleta-Gabriela and Alexandrescu, Adrian and Turcanu, Tatiana	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Empowering Education through EERP: A Customizable Educational VR Escape Room Platform	Darejeh, Ali	2023	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
A methodological proposal to learn to program through the development of video games	Puerta, Luis Norberto Zapata and Álvarez, María Clara Gómez	2018	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Enhancing Self-Motivation in Learning Programming Using Game-Based Simulation and Metrics	Jiau, Hewijin Christine and Chen, Jinghong Cox and Ssu, Kuo-Feng	2009	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Gamifying Python: Enhancing Learning Outcomes and Motivation through a Game-Based Approach	Sirikong, Nicha and Visutsak, Porawat	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Nutritional Serious-Games platform	Gago, Jesús Reseco and Barreira, Teresa Meneu and Carrascosa, Rebeca González and Segovia, Purificación García	2010	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Goos-Gambit: An Educational Card Game	Raikwar, Kanishka and Sheth, Aryan and Shrivastava, Navya and Shete, Prassanna	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Game design based learning of programming for girls	Bevčič, M. and Rugelj, J.	2020	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Exploring the Balance Between Computational Thinking and Learning Motivation in Elementary Programming Education: An Empirical Study With Game-Based Learning	Liu, Huizhong and Wu, Zengqing and Lu, Yili and Zhu, Ling	2023	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Virtual reality instructional modules for introductory programming courses	Stigall, James and Sharma, Sharad	2017	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected

Serious games for motivating into programming	Hijon-Neira, Raquel and Velázquez-Iturbide, Ángel and Pizarro-Romero, Celeste and Carriço, Luís	2014	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
NoBug's Snack Bar: A Computational Thinking Serious Game as an Educational Platform	Vahldick, Adilson and Farah, Paulo Roberto and Marcelino, Maria José and Mendes, António José Nunes	2019	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Assessing Self-Efficacy Method for Enhancing Computational Thinking in Educational Game Environment	Nobnop, Ratchanon and Chondamrongkul, Nacha and Temdee, Punnarumol	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Educational resource based on games for the reinforcement of engineering learning programming in mobile devices	Sierra, A. J. and Ariza, T. and Fernández-Jiménez, F. J. and Muñoz-Calle, J. and Molina, A. and Martín-Rodríguez, Álvaro	2016	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Difficulties of learning Programming	Abid, Chaker and Sellami, Hedia Mhiri and Ben Said, Lamjed	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
KodeAR: An OCR-AR Experience to Aid in Programming Education for Children	Ibrahim, Reda and Sharaf, Nada	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Evaluating the quality of games designed for learning programming by students with different educational background: An empirical study	Orehovački, Tihomir and Babić, Snježana	2015	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Improving Programming Learning on High School Students through Educative Apps	Montes-León, Hernán and Hijón-Neira, Raquel and Pérez-Marín, Diana and León, Sergio Raúl Montes	2019	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Video Games Platforms: A Gateway to New Trends for Initial Programming Education	Díaz, Jaime and Bustamante, Ana and Ramírez V., Gabriel M. and Hochstetter, Jorge	2022	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
PlayLOGO 3D: A 3D Interactive Video Game for Early Programming Education: Let LOGO Be a Game	Paliokas, Ioannis and Arapidis, Christos and Mpimpitsos, Michail	2011	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
A propriety game based learning mobile game to learn object-oriented programming — Odyssey of Phoenix	Wong, Yoke Seng and Hayati, Ing Maizatul and Yatim, Mohamad and Hoe, Tan Wee	2017	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Algorithmic Thinking in TVET Programming Education: An Analysis of Student Proficiency Levels and Implications	Muda, Zurina and Salleh, Kaswati and Technamurthy, Umawathy and Salleh, Syahanim Mohd	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Aligning a Serious Game, Secure Programming and CyBOK-Linked Learning Outcomes	McGregor, Léon and Chan, Sheung Chi and Wlodarczyk, Szymon and Maarek, Manuel	2022	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
An interactive serious game via visualization of real life scenarios to learn programming concepts	Sajana A. and Bijlani, Kamal and Jayakrishnan, R.	2015	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted

Serious games for effective learning	Supriana, Iping and Agustin, Ririn Dwi and Bakar, Marini Abu and Zin, Nor Azan Mat	2017	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Creating and Using Digital Educational Games in Adult Education: A Case Study in a Second Chance School in Greece	Karamerou, Vasiliki and Vergados, Dimitrios J. and Vergados, Dimitrios D.	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
jLegends: Online game to train programming skills	Tsalikidis, Konstantinos and Pavlidis, George	2016	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Transforming Programming Education: The Effectiveness of Motivational Scenario-Based Design in Serious Games	Shum, Lok Cheung and Rosunally, Yasmine and Munir, Kamran	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Learner Attitude, Educational Background, and Gender Influence on Knowledge Gain in a Serious Games-Enhanced Programming Course	Zhao, Dan and Muntean, Cristina Hava and Chis, Adriana E. and Muntean, Gabriel-Miro	2021	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Code Saga – A Mobile Serious Game For Learning Programming	Tacouri, Heeya and Nagowah, Leckraj	2021	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Investigating the Effect of the Serious Game CodeCombat on Cognitive Load in Python Programming Education	Choi, Wan Chong and Choi, Wan Chong and Choi, Iek Chong	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Integrating Serious Game in Personalized Learning Environment	Wee, Vivian Gek-Ting and Chua, Fang-Fang	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Visual Learning on Mobile Phone for Introduction Basic Programming in Vocational High School	Kurniawati, Arik and Akbar, Nurrohmat Hidayatullah and Prasetyo, Deny	2018	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Programming Education for Young People using the Falling-Puzzle Game, “Puyo Puyo”	Saito, Daisuke and Tian, Ruochen and Washizaki, Hironori and Fukazawa, Yoshiaki	2023	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Gidget: An online debugging game for learning and engagement in computing education	Lee, Michael J.	2014	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Games for Coding to Attract New Students to STEM	Calvo-Morata, Antonio and Humble, Niklas and Mozelius, Peter and Pechuel, Rasmus and Fernández-Manjón, Baltasar	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Teaching programming through games	Doherty, Liam and Kumar, Vive	2009	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Mining Learners' Behavioral Sequential Patterns in a Blockly Visual Programming Educational Game	Shih, Wen-Chung	2017	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted

Computer technology in education: Evidence from a pooled study of computer assisted learning programs among rural students in China	Di Mo and Weiming Huang and Yaojiang Shi and Linxiu Zhang and Matthew Boswell and Scott Rozelle	2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Fostering undergraduate accounting students' educational attainment through CT-enhanced collaborative project-based learning	Ting-Ting Wu and Noviati Aning Rizki Mustika Sari and Anindya Prasisca Rena Zhetira Putri and Hong-Ren Chen and Yueh-Min Huang	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
5 - Community connections	Valerie Freeman and Rebecca Freeman	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Risky business or sharing the load? – Social flow in collaborative mobile learning	Hokyoung Ryu and David Parsons	2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
Instructional Design in Modern Environments:	Sanaa Yacoub Banat and Fatima Abd-Alkareem Wahba	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Publication trends in gamification: A systematic mapping study	Jussi Kasurinen and Antti Knutas	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Proposal for a new strategy to practice programming	Lasserre, Patricia and Kotowick, Kyle	2010	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
A tangible programming system conveying event handling concept	Wang, Danli and Qi, Yunfeng and Zhang, Lan	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Digital Educational Games: Methodologies for Evaluating the Impact of Game Type	Heintz, Stephanie and Law, Effie L.-C.	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
A Practical Guide to Developing and Validating Computer Science Knowledge Assessments with Application to Middle School	Buffum, Philip Sheridan and Lobene, Eleni V. and Frankosky, Megan Hardy and Boyer, Kristy Elizabeth and Wiebe, Eric N. and Lester, James C.	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Chapter 27 - Teaching and learning for creativity in science and mathematics	Florence Gabriel and Rebecca Marrone and Kim {van Broekhoven}	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Training for Minimally Invasive Cancer Surgery	Janelle F. Rekman and Adnan Alseidi	2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 5 - Education	Sheila R. Alber-Morgan and Ron DeMuesy	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
MASACAD: A multi-agent approach to information customization for the purpose of academic advising of students	Mohamed Salah Hamdi	2007	Science@Direct	Rejected
Using inter-disciplinary programs to encourage integrated work across the curriculum	Pauline Bleach	1987	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 3 - Security and privacy in healthcare blockchain	R. Saranya and Pankaj Bhambri	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
Research and Education Posters Presented at the 121st Virtual Annual Meeting of the American Association of Colleges of Pharmacy, July 13-31, 2020		2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Editor's choice 2007: Selected online learning resources		2007	Science@Direct	Rejected
APhA2018 abstracts of contributed papers		2018	Science@Direct	Rejected

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Abstracts Presented at the 120th Annual Meeting of the American Association of Colleges of Pharmacy, Chicago, Illinois, July 13-17, 2019		2019	Science@Direct	Rejected
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2015 American Association of Colleges of Pharmacy Annual Report: Message from the President and the Executive Vice President and CEO		2015	Science@Direct	Rejected
Game2Learn: building CS1 learning games for retention	Barnes, Tiffany and Richter, Heather and Powell, Eve and Chaffin, Amanda and Godwin, Alex	2007	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Pyrus: Designing A Collaborative Programming Game to Promote Problem Solving Behaviors	Shi, Joshua and Shah, Armaan and Hedman, Garrett and O'Rourke, Eleanor	2019	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Teaching Object Oriented Programming Concepts Through a Mobile Serious Game	Lotfi, Elaachak and Mohammed, Bouhorma	2018	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Programming as a Performance: Live-streaming and Its Implications for Computer Science Education	Haaranen, Lassi	2017	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
An Empirical Study on the Effect of Gamified Teaching in Scratch Courses on Developing Elementary Students' Computational Thinking	Chen, Yuxi and Zhao, Yang and Wang, Min	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
C++ Adventure: A Mixed Methods Pilot Study on Digital Game-Based Learning of Coding and Effect on Motivation	Cu Hao, Lester and Delantar, Ma. Buena and Tan, Giselle Jasmine	2021	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Play, Learn, Code: Assessing the Efficacy of Gamification in Computer Programming 1 Instruction	Rey, William P and Defensor, Kristel Eunice R	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Serious Games for Enhancing Accessibility Awareness and Skills	Parthasarathy, P.D. and Joshi, Swaroop	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Microworlds, Games and Collaboration: three effective approaches to support novices in learning programming	Xinogalos, Stelios and Malliarakis, Christos and Tsompanoudi, Despina and Satratzemi, Maya	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ETRA '25: Proceedings of the 2025 Symposium on Eye Tracking Research and Applications		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHI EA '24: Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
EDCS '25: Proceedings of the 2nd Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area Education Digitalization and Computer Science International Conference		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICDEL '23: Proceedings of the 2023 8th International Conference on Distance Education and Learning		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IDC '23: Proceedings of the 22nd Annual ACM Interaction Design and Children Conference		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
RESPECT 2024: Proceedings of the 2024 on RESPECT Annual Conference		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Mindtrek '25: Proceedings of the 28th International Academic Mindtrek Conference		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHIGreece '25: Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference of the ACM Greek SIGCHI Chapter		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IDC '24: Proceedings of the 23rd Annual ACM Interaction Design and Children Conference		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
AIFE '25: Proceedings of the 2025 2nd International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Future Education		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SBES '23: Proceedings of the XXXVII Brazilian Symposium on Software Engineering		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SBSI '24: Proceedings of the 20th Brazilian Symposium on Information Systems		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
AVI '24: Proceedings of the 2024 International Conference on Advanced Visual Interfaces		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
FDG '23: Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on the Foundations of Digital Games		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
EASE '24: Proceedings of the 28th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
C&C '25: Proceedings of the 2025 Conference on Creativity and Cognition		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
EASEAI 2022: Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Education through Advanced Software Engineering and Artificial Intelligence		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Values at play: design tradeoffs in socially-oriented game design	Flanagan, Mary and Howe, Daniel C. and Nissenbaum, Helen	2005	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Achieving Gender Balance through Creative Expression	Bares, William H. and Manaris, Bill and McCauley, Ren'e and Moore, Christine	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
The next decade of the database course: three decades speak to the next	Springsteel, Frederick and Robbert, Mary Ann and Ricardo, Catherine M.	2000	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
O-Mopsi: Mobile Orienteering Game for Sightseeing, Exercising, and Education	Franti, Pasi and Mariescu-Istodor, Radu and Sengupta, Lahari	2017	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICETT '24: Proceedings of the 2024 10th International Conference on Education and Training Technologies		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Game2Learn: improving the motivation of CS1 students	Barnes, Tiffany and Powell, Eve and Chaffin, Amanda and Lipford, Heather	2008	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
"Rules or Data? Gotta Catch 'Em All!": A Tangible Game for Youth AI Literacy	Li, Zihan and Goswami, Lahari and Feng, Yuqing and Williams, Kristin and Yi Wang, April	2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ITICSE-WGR '23: Proceedings of the 2023 Working Group Reports on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Learning programming with peer support, games, challenges and scratch	Bittencourt, Roberto A. and dos Santos, David Moises B. and Rodrigues, Carlos A. and Batista, Washington P. and Chalegre, Henderson S.	2015	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
A Game-Based Learning Approach on Robotics Visualization for Loops in Programming Concepts	Thanyaphongphat, Jirapipat and Thongkoo, Krittawaya and Daungcharone, Kannika and Areeprayolkij, Wantana	2020	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Preliminary results of a freshmen capstone project to design educational modules for teachers in the dominican republic	Reeping, David and Estell, John K. and Reid, Kenneth	2014	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Integrating Learning Analytics in an Educational MMORPG for Computer Programming	Malliarakis, Christos and Satratzemi, Maya and Xinogalos, Stelios	2014	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Utilizing a Serious Game via Open Sim Standalone Server and Scratch4OS for Introductory Programming Courses in Secondary Education: Their Effect on Student Engagement	Pellas, Nikolaos and Konstantinou, Nikolaos and Georgiou, Georgia and Malliarakis, Christos and Kazanidis, Ioannis	2014	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Using a Serious Game Approach to Teach 'Operator Precedence' to Introductory Programming Students	Adamo-Villani, Nicoletta and Haley-Hermiz, Thomas and Cutler, Robb	2013	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Analysis of the learning effects between text-based and visual-based beginner programming environments	Saito, Daisuke and Washizaki, Hironori and Fukazawa, Yoshiaki	2016	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
An AI-Powered Application to Enhance Cognitive Health and Provide Caregiver Support for Dementia Patients	Lulle, Kirti and Agrawal, Pooja and Amrutwar, Mansi and Khiani, Simran	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Programming Games as Learning Tools: Using Empathic Design Principles for Engaging Experiences	Maxim, Raluca Ionela and Arnedo-Moreno, Joan	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Programming Education Through Game-Based Learning and Quizzes	Bubenkova, Lenka and Pietrikova, Emilia	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Accepted
Poké Prog: Jogo educacional para o ensino dos conceitos básicos de programação	Jeanluca Abreu and Hugo Castro and Clausius Reis and Pedro Sousa	2023	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Accepted
Impact of extended reality on architectural education and the design process	Farzam Kharvari and Lorenz Ewald Kaiser	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Nutrition Education and Behavioral Sciences		2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
112th Annual Meeting of the American Association of Colleges of Pharmacy, San Antonio, TX, July 9-13, 2011		2011	Science@Direct	Rejected

Critical Review on the Impact of ICT Among Undergraduate Students	C.G. Sijimol	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
The impact of simulation-enhanced interprofessional education on student knowledge and satisfaction: A multivariate analysis across fields of study	Valerie M. Wright and Antony R. Joseph and Patricia L. Pence and Susan Watkins	2026	Science@Direct	Rejected
A snapshot of the readiness for e-learning among in-service teachers prior to the pandemic-related transition to e-learning in Turkey	Murat Çınar and Murat Ekici and Ömer Demir	2021	Science@Direct	Rejected
Use of the ARCS model in education: A literature review	Kun Li and John M. Keller	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Bronchoscopy Education: An Experiential Learning Theory Perspective	Septimiu D. Murgu and Jonathan S. Kurman and Omar Hasan	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
A systematic review of library makerspaces research	Soo Hyeon Kim and Yong Ju Jung and Gi Woong Choi	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Effectiveness of Educational Interventions to Increase Knowledge of Evidence-Based Practice Among Nurses and Physiotherapists in Primary Health Care: Protocol for a Systematic Review	Henk Verloo and Pauline Melly and Roger Hilfiker and Filipa Pereira	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Accounting education literature review (2016)	Barbara Apostolou and Jack W. Dorminey and John M. Hassell and James E. Rebele	2017	Science@Direct	Rejected
Artificial intelligence in Ethiopian school curriculum: Educators' practices, challenges, and recommendations	Fitsum Gizachew Deriba and Ismaila Temitayo Sanusi	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Talent development gamification in talent selection assessment centres	Carole Tansley and Ella Hafermalz and Kristine Dery	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
An E-learning outreach program for public schools: Findings and lessons learned based on a pilot program in Makati City and Cabuyao City, Laguna, Philippines	Rhoderick V. Nuncio and Myla M. Arcinas and Rochelle Irene G. Lucas and Jasper Vincent Q. Alontaga and Susan Grace T. Neri and Jose Mari Carpena	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
Intergenerational collaborative dynamics in digital game design learning: A sequential analysis of communication patterns	Ya-Ling Wang and Chih-Chi Liu and Chih-Chen Kuo and Huei-Tse Hou	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Experience of Using Simulation Technology and Analytics During the Ebola Crisis to Empower Frontline Health Workers and Improve the Integrity of Public Health Systems	Nicholas Mellor and Hetty Horton and David Luke and Jon Meadows and Arunangsu Chatterjee and Thomas Gale	2016	Science@Direct	Rejected
Artificial intelligence (AI)-assisted HRM: Towards an extended strategic framework	Ashish Malik and Pawan Budhwar and Bahar Ali Kazmi	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected
Students' perceptions of collaboration, self-regulated learning, and information seeking in the context of Internet-based learning and traditional learning	Silvia Wen-Yu Lee and Chin-Chung Tsai	2011	Science@Direct	Rejected
Educational Mobile Games as a Tool for Increasing Vocabulary When Learning a Foreign Language	Valentina Panfilova and Valentina Spichak and Anargul Zhumakhanova	2022	Science@Direct	Rejected
Chapter 1 - Interactivity and the Writer	Timothy Garrand	2006	Science@Direct	Rejected

Exploring the computational thinking effects in pre-university education	Francisco José García-Peñalvo and António José Mendes	2018	Science@Direct	Rejected
Design and Development of Learn Your Way Out: A Gamified Content for Basic Java Computer Programming	Nerico L. Mingoc and Erik Louwe R. Sala	2019	Science@Direct	Accepted
Comparative experiment of the effects of unplugged and plugged-in programming on computational thinking in primary school students: A perspective of multiple influential factors	Lihui Sun and Junjie Liu and Yunshan Liu	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Motivational aspects of different learning contexts: "My mom won't let me play this game..."	Ivana Kovačević and Miroslav Minović and Miloš Milovanović and Patricia Ordoñez {de Pablos} and Dušan Starčević	2013	Science@Direct	Rejected
Learning experience assessment through players chat content in multiplayer online games	Mohammad Mahdi Rezapour and Afsaneh Fatemi and Mohammad Ali Nematbakhsh	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
The role of AI in shaping educational experiences in computer science: A systematic review	Anahita Golrang and Kshitij Sharma	2025	Science@Direct	Rejected
Evaluating the efficacy of computer games-based learning intervention in enhancing English speaking proficiency	Omar Al-Jamili and Musharraf Aziz and Fathey Mohammed and Abdullah Almogahed and Abdulwadood Alawadhi	2024	Science@Direct	Rejected
Classifying the tools of contextualized programming education and forms of media computation	Lukkarinen, Alekski and Sorva, Juha	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
A systematic review of approaches for teaching introductory programming and their influence on success	Vihavainen, Arto and Airaksinen, Jonne and Watson, Christopher	2014	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Mobile Escape Rooms for Learning Programming in Nigerian Higher Institutions	Chinedu Ugo, Chidera	2024	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
DeliverC: Teaching Pointers through GenAI-Powered Game-Based Learning	Petula, Wyatt and Joshi, Anushcka and Tu, Peggy and Somasundar, Amrutha and Saha, Suman	2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Enhancing Programming Education through Game-Based Learning: Design and Implementation of a Puyo Puyo-Inspired Teaching Tool	Tian, Ruochen and Saito, Daisuke and Washizaki, Hironori and Fukazawa, Yoshiaki and Kobayashi, Hiroshi and Tsuji, Ayumi	2024	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
Evaluation of Simulation Games for Teaching Engineering and Manufacturing	Jannicke Baalsrud Hauge and Johann C.K.H. Riedel	2012	Science@Direct	Rejected
Data mining for providing a personalized learning path in creativity: An application of decision trees	Chun Fu Lin and Yu-chu Yeh and Yu Hsin Hung and Ray I Chang	2013	Science@Direct	Rejected
Enhancing student's computational thinking skills with student-generated questions strategy in a game-based learning platform	Yu-Ping Cheng and Chin-Feng Lai and Yun-Ting Chen and Wei-Sheng Wang and Yueh-Min Huang and Ting-Ting Wu	2023	Science@Direct	Rejected

Development and Evaluation of Intelligent Serious Games for Children With Learning Difficulties: Observational Study	Andrej Flogie and Boris Aberšek and Metka {Kordigel Aberšek} and Cecilia {Sik Lanyi} and Igor Pesek	2020	Science@Direct	Rejected
GABALL Project: Serious Games Based Language Learning	Saulute Juzeleniene and Jurgita Mikelioniene and Paula Escudeiro and Carlos Vaz de Carvalho	2014	Science@Direct	Rejected
NordiCHI '22: Nordic Human-Computer Interaction Conference		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
VRST '19: Proceedings of the 25th ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology		2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
FSE 2016: Proceedings of the 2016 24th ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering		2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
MuC '24: Proceedings of Mensch und Computer 2024		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
MuC '25: Proceedings of the Mensch und Computer 2025		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ASE '22: Proceedings of the 37th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHI '21: Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems		2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICEKIM '25: Proceedings of the 2025 6th International Conference on Education, Knowledge and Information Management		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
TEI '24: Proceedings of the Eighteenth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICAIE '24: Proceedings of the 2024 3rd International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Education		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
TEI '26: Proceedings of the Twentieth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction		2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ETAIC '25: Proceedings of the 2025 International Conference on Educational Technology and Artificial Intelligence		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHI '24: Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ETRA '23: Proceedings of the 2023 Symposium on Eye Tracking Research and Applications		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
DIS '25: Proceedings of the 2025 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHI '23: Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICSE-SEIS '23: Proceedings of the 45th International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering in Society		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CompSysTech '23: Proceedings of the 24th International Conference on Computer Systems and Technologies		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

CUI '24: Proceedings of the 6th ACM Conference on Conversational User Interfaces		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IECA '25: Proceedings of the 2025 2nd International Conference on Informatics Education and Computer Technology Applications		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
UIST Adjunct '25: Adjunct Proceedings of the 38th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Outreach for improved student performance: a game design and development curriculum	Doran, Katelyn and Boyce, Acey and Finkelstein, Samantha and Barnes, Tiffany	2012	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IC4E '23: Proceedings of the 2023 14th International Conference on E-Education, E-Business, E-Management and E-Learning		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICEMT '23: Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Education and Multimedia Technology		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SAC '24: Proceedings of the 39th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Graphical game development in CS2: a flexible infrastructure for a semester long project	Lewis, Mark C. and Massingill, Berna	2006	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
HT '25: Proceedings of the 36th ACM Conference on Hypertext and Social Media		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHIWORK '24: Proceedings of the 3rd Annual Meeting of the Symposium on Human-Computer Interaction for Work		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
EASE Companion '25: Proceedings of the 2025 29th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering Companion		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CHI EA '23: Extended Abstracts of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SBSI '23: Proceedings of the XIX Brazilian Symposium on Information Systems		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ISSTA 2024: Proceedings of the 33rd ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Software Testing and Analysis		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
The story engine concept in CS education	Shultz, Gerald A.	2004	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICETM '22: Proceedings of the 2022 5th International Conference on Education Technology Management		2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
C&C '23: Proceedings of the 15th Conference on Creativity and Cognition		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
dg.o '23: Proceedings of the 24th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
SA '23: SIGGRAPH Asia 2023 Art Papers		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
IC4E '24: Proceedings of the 2024 15th International Conference on E-Education, E-Business, E-Management and E-Learning		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
UMAP Adjunct '24: Adjunct Proceedings of the 32nd ACM Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

ISS Companion '24: Companion Proceedings of the 2024 Conference on Interactive Surfaces and Spaces		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
PCI '24: Proceedings of the 28th Pan-Hellenic Conference on Progress in Computing and Informatics		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
LAK '25: Proceedings of the 15th International Learning Analytics and Knowledge Conference		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
LAK '24: Proceedings of the 14th Learning Analytics and Knowledge Conference		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICEDS '23: Proceedings of the 2023 4th International Conference on Education Development and Studies		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ECSEE '23: Proceedings of the 5th European Conference on Software Engineering Education		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ECSEE '25: Proceedings of the 6th European Conference on Software Engineering Education		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Balancing Support and Struggle: An Experience Report on Token-Based Help-Seeking in a Data Structures Course	Madooei, Ali	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Motivating High School Girls to Study Computer Science	Gutica, Mirela	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICMET '24: Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Modern Educational Technology		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
User Affect and No-Match Dialogue Scenarios: An Analysis of Facial Expression	Wiggins, Joseph B. and Kulkarni, Mayank and Min, Wookhee and Boyer, Kristy Elizabeth and Mott, Bradford and Wiebe, Eric and Lester, James	2018	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Systematic Literature Review on Project-Based Learning in Computing Education	Suleiman, Ahmad D. and Hou, Daqing and Liu, Yu and DeWaters, Jan and Shepherd, David C. and G. De Souza, Juliana	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
'Too Theoretical and Nowhere Near Interesting': Using a Tool to Increase Student Motivation for Formal Methods	Brought, Katherine and Li, Yangge and Driggs-Campbell, Katherine and Mitra, Sayan	2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Brief review of video games in learning & education how far we have come	Kenwright, Ben	2017	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICBDE '24: Proceedings of the 2024 7th International Conference on Big Data and Education		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
GamiFIN '26: Proceedings of the 10th Annual International GamiFIN Conference 2026		2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Exploring Computer Science Topics with Programmable Smartwatches	Niu, Shuo and Esakia, Andrey and McCrickard, Scott	2015	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Games for learning: bridging game-related education methods to software engineering knowledge areas	Souza, Mauricio R A and Veado, Lucas and Moreira, Renata Teles and Figueiredo, Eduardo and Costa, Heitor	2017	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

ITiCSE 2024: 2024 Working Group Reports on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Distractors in Parsons Problems Decrease Learning Efficiency for Young Novice Programmers	Harms, Kyle James and Chen, Jason and Kelleher, Caitlin L.	2016	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ICER '25: Proceedings of the 2025 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research V.1		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CompEd 2023: Proceedings of the ACM Conference on Global Computing Education Vol 1		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Exploring Differences in Minority Students' Attitudes towards Computing after a One-Day Coding Workshop	Lee, Michael J.	2019	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ITiCSE 2024: Proceedings of the 2024 on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education V. 1		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Exploring How Game Genre in Student-Designed Games Influences Computational Thinking Development	Troiano, Giovanni Maria and Chen, Qinyu and Alba, \{A\}ngela Vargas and Robles, Gregorio and Smith, Gillian and Cassidy, Michael and Tucker-Raymond, Eli and Puttick, Gillian and Harteveld, Casper	2020	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Bug-eecha: A Gamified Approach to Programming Problem Comprehension and Testing	Kumar, Viraj and Joseph, Amrit M. and Sarma, Soumyadeep and Shelly	2023	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
COMPUTE '23: Proceedings of the 16th Annual ACM India Compute Conference		2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
When Children Program Intelligent Environments: Lessons Learned from a Serious AR Game	Stefanidi, Evropi and Korozi, Maria and Leonidis, Asterios and Arampatzis, Dimitrios and Antona, Margherita and Papagiannakis, George	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Towards a feature-based didactic framework for generating individualized programming tasks for an e-learning environment	Willert, Nico and Eriksson, Janik	2023	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Koli Calling '24: Proceedings of the 24th Koli Calling International Conference on Computing Education Research		2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Toward a Gamified Approach Based on Augmented Resources in Education	El Hassan, Abdelwahed and Nabou, Abdellah and Jaouar, Maria and Ez-Zarzouri, Houda and Qazdar, Imad and Belfarji, Khawla	2024	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
ACE '26: Proceedings of the 28th Australasian Computing Education Conference		2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
CompEd 2025: Proceedings of the ACM Global Computing Education Conference 2025 - Volume 2		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected

Explanations of Data Systems Concepts in CS Education: An Updated View on Notional Machines	Miedema, Daphne and Goodfellow, Martin and Satyavolu, Chandrika and Haldeman, Georgiana and Busuttil, Leonard and Farinetti, Laura and Guerrini, Giovanna and Pan, Yuhan and Ramagoni, Sujeeth Goud and Sooriamurthi, Raja and Tu, Xiaoying	2026	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Are They Learning or Playing? Moderator Conditions of Gamification's Success in Programming Classrooms	Rodrigues, Luiz and Pereira, Filipe and Toda, Armando and Palomino, Paula and Oliveira, Wilk and Pessoa, Marcela and Carvalho, Leandro and Oliveira, David and Oliveira, Elaine and Cristea, Alexandra and Isotani, Seiji	2022	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
Teaching Programming with Gamified Semantics	Arawjo, Ian and Wang, Cheng-Yao and Myers, Andrew C. and Andersen, Erik and Guimbretière, François	2017	ACM Digital Library	Accepted
CompEd 2025: Proceedings of the ACM Global Computing Education Conference 2025 - Volume 1		2025	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
A Game-Based Approach for Teaching Algorithms and Data Structures using Visualizations	Su, Simon and Zhang, Edward and Denny, Paul and Giacaman, Nasser	2021	ACM Digital Library	Rejected
How can a simulation game support the development of computational problem-solving strategies?	Pellas, Nikolaos and Vosinakis, Spyridon	2017	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected
Curriculum, Teaching and Learning, and Assessments for Introductory Programming Course	Mehmood, Erum and Abid, Adnan and Farooq, Muhammad Shoaib and Nawaz, Naeem A.	2020	IEEE Digital Library	Rejected